

Social Workers in the Policy Process:
A Case Study of Swiss Social Workers' Policy Engagement

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Abstract

This article-based dissertation examines social workers' policy engagement through an in-depth analysis of their involvement in a highly contested reform of social assistance in Switzerland. Anchored in the Swiss political system and the real-world case of proposed reductions to social assistance in the canton of Bern between 2012 and 2019, the dissertation addresses three interrelated research questions: (1) What are the key political institutions in Switzerland and how do they affect social workers' policy engagement? (2) When, and in which roles, do social workers become involved in policy processes? (3) What policy engagement strategies do social workers employ?

To address these questions, the dissertation brings together three complementary articles. Adopting a conceptual perspective, the first article addresses the first research question by analysing the key political institutions in Switzerland and examines how these institutions influence social workers' policy engagement. The second article responds to the second and third research questions by zooming in on the contested Bern case. Drawing on thematic analysis of interviews and documentary sources, it reconstructs the unfolding of this policy process and investigates when, how, and in which roles social workers became involved. The third article further develops the third research question by providing a deeper account of the strategies employed by social workers to influence the policy process in Bern. Based on thematic analysis of interviews with social workers engaged in the case, it identifies and describes seven distinct policy strategies in detail.

Taken together, the dissertation offers one of the few empirical insights into social workers' engagement within a real policy process. Using the Bern case as a focal point, it develops a nuanced understanding of when and how social workers engage in policymaking, the roles they adopt and the political institutions that provide opportunities for their engagement. Across these dimensions, the study advances theoretical concepts and formulates

practical implications aimed at strengthening policy engagement as a core dimension of the social work profession.

Statement of contribution

This dissertation was carried out under the supervision of Professor John Gal and Professor Stefan Köngeter. Professor Simone Leiber and Professor Roni Holler served as members of the advisory committee. Tobias Kindler was the sole author of the three manuscripts submitted as part of this dissertation. His contributions included the conceptualization of the study, data collection and analysis, manuscript writing and editing, as well as full participation in the publication process. Apart from the doctoral supervisors, no additional contributors were involved in the research project.

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When you are reading this, you will most likely already have caught a glimpse of the colourful title page. I would like to express my sincere thanks to Henriette Sonntag for her work enriching this otherwise text-focussed dissertation with a playful element.

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CHAPTER 1 – INTRODUCTION

This dissertation is based on three articles that have been published in, or are currently under review at, peer-reviewed journals. It contributes to the evolving discourse on the policy engagement of social workers by examining their involvement in the planned cuts to social assistance in the canton of Bern in Switzerland between 2012 and 2019. Using this case as its empirical foundation, the dissertation provides a contextualised understanding of when and how social workers engage in policy processes, the roles they assume and the political institutions that enable or constrain such engagement. This introductory chapter presents the relevance of the study in the context of existing conceptual and empirical scholarship, outlines the overarching research aim and guiding questions, provides an overview of the methodological approach, and sets out the dissertation's structure.

1.1 Conceptual and empirical background

Policy engagement – understood as the intentional effort to contribute to the development, adaptation, opposition or evaluation of policies – has long been recognised as a central dimension of social work practice (Gal & Weiss-Gal, 2023a; Jansson, 2018; Lane & Pritzker, 2018). The commitment to influencing policy is explicitly articulated in key ethical and professional documents, including the international definition of social work (IASSW and IFSW, 2014) and national codes of ethics such as those in Australia (AASW, 2020), Germany (DBSH, 2024), Hong Kong (SWRB, 2013), the United Kingdom (BASW, 2021), the United States (NASW, 2021), or Switzerland (AvenirSocial, 2026). These documents highlight the profession's dual mandate to provide support to groups and individuals while simultaneously promoting structural change. This dual responsibility positions social workers not merely as implementers of existing policies but also as active contributors to policy development.

Despite these normative calls, scholarship on social workers' policy engagement remains comparatively limited. Systematic attention to how, when, and why social workers

engage in policy has only recently begun to emerge (Gal & Weiss-Gal, 2023b; Weiss-Gal, 2016, 2017). Much of the existing body of work originates from the United States (e.g. Atteberry-Ash et al., 2023; Epstein, 1968; Hoefler, 2013; Lane et al., 2018; Ostrander et al., 2018; Pence & Kaiser, 2023; Wathen et al., 2025) and Israel (e.g. Gal & Weiss, 2000; Nouman et al., 2020; Schwartz-Tayri, 2021; Weiss, 2003; Weiss-Gal & Gal, 2020, 2025), where the topic has a well-established tradition of inquiry. In recent years, however, a broader and more diverse range of scholarship has developed, encompassing conceptual and empirical contributions from various regions, including Albania (Dauti & Bejko, 2024, 2025), Australia (e.g. Hallam & Mendes, 2025; Mendes, 2013; Morley et al., 2025; Pawar, 2019), Austria (e.g. Kohlfürst, 2025; Kohlfürst & Kulke, 2018), Belgium (e.g. Brussee et al. 2025; De Corte & Roose, 2020; Naert et al., 2024; Rombaut & Raeymaeckers, 2025), Canada (e.g. McLaughlin et al., 2019; Shewell et al., 2021), China (e.g. Cai et al., 2022; Jin et al., 2017; Zhang et al., 2021), Czechia (e.g. Balaz, 2023, Zogata-Kusz & Matulayová, 2025), Egypt (e.g. Abo El Nasr, 1991), Ethiopia (e.g. Baynesagn, 2020), Finland (e.g. Kallio et al., 2024; Kroll et al., 2025; Salonen et al., 2025), Germany (e.g. Birwer & Schäfer, 2023; Burzlaff, 2022; Dischler & Kulke, 2021; Einhorn et al., 2026; Kessler, 2022; Klöckner, 2025; Köngeter, 2023, 2025; Kulke & Schmidt, 2019; Leiber et al., 2023; Leitner & Stolz, 2023; Löffler, 2024; Rieger, 2024; Schein, 2026; Schierer & Müller, 2025), Hong Kong (e.g. Chui & Gray, 2004; Mok, 1988; Ngai, 2005; Wong et al., 2025), Italy (e.g. Campanini & Facchini, 2013; Fargion, 2018; Guidi et al., 2025), Greece (e.g. Efstathiou et al., 2025), Kenya (e.g. Muraguri & Malinda, 2022), New Zealand (e.g. Darroch, 2023; Webster, 2021), Poland (Poławski, 2019), Portugal (e.g. Carrilho & Branco, 2023; Carvalho et al., 2025; Costa et al., 2025; Silva, 2018), Puerto Rico (e.g. Negrón-Velázquez, 2017), Russia (Iarskaia-Smirnova & Romanov, 2013), South Korea (e.g. Kim et al., 2023; Shin, 2022), Spain (e.g. Martínez-Román, 2013; Murcia Álvarez, 2024; Sánchez Castiñeira,

2019), South Africa (e.g. Lombard, 2017), Sweden (e.g. Bečević & Herz, 2023; Tham & Thorén, 2020; Thorén & Salonen, 2013), Switzerland (e.g. Amann & Kindler, 2022; Demircali et al., 2024; Kehl, 2023), Tanzania (e.g. Manyama, 2018), Turkey (e.g. Bozdemir & Kılıç Ceyhan, 2020; Güzel & Selçuk, 2025; Topper, 2022), the United Kingdom (e.g. Gwilym, 2017; Scourfield & Warner, 2022; Simpson, 2013), and Zimbabwe (e.g. Muchanyerei, 2017; Mungwari, 2025), as well as a number of international comparative studies (e.g. Gal & Weiss-Gal, 2013, 2017; Gray et al., 2002; Ioakimidis et al., 2014; Kindler et al., 2025; Kindler & Kulke, 2022; Ostrander et al., 2021; Toens & Rieger, 2025; Weiss et al., 2002, 2005). This expansion of the scholarly landscape reflects a growing recognition of the significance of policy engagement across different social, political, and professional contexts.

This body of international scholarship has so far explored social workers' policy engagement along four main dimensions: (1) the strategies they employ to influence policy, (2) the professional roles through which they participate, (3) their engagement in the dynamics of policy processes, and (4) the factors that shape their involvement. The following sections provide an overview of existing scholarship along these dimensions and delineate how the present dissertation extends and deepens the discourse within this emerging field of knowledge.

1.1.1 Social workers' strategies of policy engagement

Existing scholarship has identified a wide range of social workers' policy strategies, understood here as the concrete activities and broader approaches through which social workers seek to influence the development, adaptation, opposition or evaluation of policies. These strategies include advocating for legislative and electoral change, holding elected office, pursuing reform through litigation, engaging in social action, conducting policy analysis, engaging service users in policy processes, and implementing policy (e.g. Benz &

Rieger, 2015; Figueira-McDonough, 1993; Jansson, 1984, 2018; Lane & Pritzker, 2018; Ritter, 2026; Weiss-Gal, 2017; Wyers, 1991).

To systematise these diverse approaches, the insider-outsider typology offers a useful heuristic framework. Originating in the study of interest groups, this typology distinguishes between insiders, who enjoy privileged access to decision-making processes, and outsiders, who – being either unable or unwilling to pursue the insider route – seek to exert influence through indirect means (Almog-Bar, 2018; Binderkrantz, 2005; Carbert, 2004; Grant, 2004). Early scholarship tended to assume a strong correspondence between a group's status and its strategy: insider groups were expected to employ insider strategies, involving direct engagement with policymakers through formal and informal channels, whereas outsider groups were assumed to rely primarily on outsider strategies aimed at raising awareness and mobilising the public through both conflictual and non-conflictual means (Grant, 2000). More recent scholarship, however, has shown that although these general patterns persist, the boundaries between strategies are more fluid. Insider groups frequently employ outsider strategies, while outsider groups also engage in certain forms of insider activity (Cailleux, 2025; Wagner et al., 2023). Although the insider-outsider typology was originally developed to examine the policy strategies of interest groups, it has proven equally valuable for characterising individual policy engagement, including those undertaken by social workers (e.g. De Corte & Roose, 2020).

Focusing specifically on social workers, Guidi et al. (2025) and Rieger (2014, 2021) propose alternative frameworks for conceptualising policy strategies. Both distinguish between internal strategies, aimed at influencing organisational policies, and external strategies, directed towards the formulation of public policy at local, regional, state or international level. They also distinguish between direct and indirect policy strategies, albeit with differing emphases: Rieger (2014, 2021) defines direct strategies as forms of advocacy

undertaken on behalf of service users, while indirect strategies centre on empowering service users and facilitating their self-advocacy. By contrast, Guidi et al. (2025) conceptualise direct strategies as those directed towards policymakers – analogous to the insider strategies discussed above – whereas indirect strategies are aimed at shaping the views of other stakeholders who, in turn, engage with policymakers, thus aligning with the previously discussed outsider strategies.

Empirical research on social workers' policy strategies consistently indicates that social workers tend to favour consensus-oriented and collaborative strategies rather than conflictual or adversarial ones (Cai et al., 2024; Dauti & Bejko, 2025; Gal & Weiss-Gal, 2023b; Gilboa & Weiss-Gal, 2022; Reeser & Epstein, 1987, 1990). Moreover, scholarship has shown that social workers are more likely to engage in passive rather than active policy strategies – that is, activities requiring less time, specialised knowledge, or public visibility (Ostrander et al., 2018; Lane et al., 2018; Mary, 2001; Makaros et al., 2020; Parker & Sherraden, 1991; Ritter, 2007; Rome & Hoechstetter, 2010). Previous studies have further demonstrated that social workers tend to focus their policy engagement primarily on influencing the policies of their own organisations, while being less involved in policy change efforts at the local, regional, national, or international levels (Burzlaff, 2025; Carvalho et al., 2025; Guidi et al., 2025; Weiss-Gal et al., 2020).

Taken together, these conceptual and empirical strands indicate that social workers' policy strategies are predominantly consensus-oriented, aimed at advocating on behalf of service users, and primarily focused on policy change at the organisational level. However, while these previous studies provide valuable insights, their largely quantitative approaches (Weiss-Gal, 2017) tend to produce abstract and aggregated findings that may obscure additional policy strategies embedded in social work practice. Qualitative research and case studies examining real-life policy processes – which could illuminate social workers' policy

strategies in more contextualised and nuanced ways – remain notably scarce (e.g. Aviv et al., 2021; Gal & Weiss-Gal, 2025; Ngai, 2005; Tayeb Elmakias, 2025; Tzadiki & Weiss-Gal, 2021). One part of the present dissertation addresses this gap by examining the policy strategies of social workers in the context of the real-world policy case of planned reductions to social assistance in the canton of Bern.

1.1.2 Social workers' professional roles and policy engagement

Previous scholarship has also examined social workers' involvement in policymaking in relation to their professional roles, understood here as the combination of their primary field of practice, organisational affiliation, hierarchical position, and forms of engagement. Research in this area has investigated the professional roles through which social workers participate in policy processes and has begun to analyse how these roles influence both the extent and the strategies of their policy engagement.

A useful conceptual tool for examining social workers' roles is the Policy Engagement Conceptual Framework developed by Gal and Weiss-Gal (2015, 2023a). This framework differentiates between social workers' policy engagement in civic roles outside working hours and their involvement in professional roles within the context of employment. The civic routes encompass serving as a politician or engaging in voluntary political participation as a private individual. In contrast, professional routes include policy practice and street-level policy involvement as practitioners, academic policy engagement as social work scholars, and policy involvement through professional organisations in which social workers participate as members, staff members, or board representatives.

Empirical research drawing on factors included in the Policy Engagement Conceptual Framework has focused on policy engagement associated with specific roles. For example, previous studies have explored how social workers influence policy in their roles as politicians (Binder & Weiss-Gal, 2022; Gwilym, 2017; Hallam & Mendes, 2025; Lane & Humphreys,

2011; Leitner & Stolz, 2023; Löffler, 2024; McLaughlin et al., 2019; Meehan, 2019; Kindler et al., 2025; Pence & Kaiser, 2023), private individuals (Kim et al., 2023; Kindler & Ostrander, 2022; Ostrander et al., 2021; Ritter, 2008; Wathen et al., 2025), frontline practitioners (Burzlaff et al., 2025; Carvalho et al., 2025; Guidi et al., 2025; Tayeb Elmakias, 2025), policy entrepreneurs (Aviv et al., 2021; Cohen, 2021; Lavee & Cohen, 2019; Nouman & Cohen, 2023; Zhang et al., 2021), leaders in social work professional organisations (Beimers, 2015; Guidi, 2020, 2025a, 2025b; Hartnett et al., 2005; Mendes, 2003; Pawlak & Flynn, 1990), and social work scholars (Baynesagn, 2020; Crisp, 2025; Gal & Weiss-Gal, 2017; Köngeter et al., 2018; Morley et al., 2025; Shewell et al., 2021; Tham & Thorén, 2020).

These studies make valuable contributions by describing and explaining how social workers in specific roles engage in policy processes. Nevertheless, research examining policy engagement among social workers across different professional roles remains limited. Initial investigations in this area focused on the influence of hierarchical position, finding that social workers in managerial roles tend to be more involved in policy activities than frontline practitioners (Burzlaff et al., under review; Gal & Weiss-Gal, 2025; Weiss-Gal & Gal, 2020). Further studies have shown that levels of policy engagement vary across fields of practice, with community social workers being the most actively involved in policy-related work (Kulke & Schmidt, 2019; Weiss-Gal et al., 2020). Findings on the influence of organisational affiliation are mixed: Mary (2001) found that social workers in the United States employed in public organisations were more engaged in policymaking than those in private settings, whereas Dauti and Bejko (2024) reported that Albanian social workers in international and civil society organisations demonstrated higher levels of policy engagement than their counterparts in governmental agencies.

While existing studies have explored policy engagement associated with specific professional roles, analyses across different roles remain limited. Consequently, it is not yet

clear how different professional roles influence both the opportunities and the forms of policy engagement available to social workers. To extend these insights, one part of the present dissertation investigates the fields of practice, organisational affiliations, hierarchical positions, and forms of engagement through which social workers participated in the policy process concerning the planned reductions in social assistance in the canton of Bern.

1.1.3 Social workers' engagement in the dynamics of policy processes

In addition to examining the strategies and roles underpinning social workers' policy engagement, recent scholarship has begun to explore the timing of their involvement in policy processes. This emerging strand of empirical research has sought to analyse when social workers engage in policymaking, often employing the policy cycle framework as an analytical lens. Although this framework has been critiqued for oversimplifying the complex, iterative, and non-linear character of policy processes (e.g. Benz & Rieger, 2015; Cairney, 2020; Hoefler, 2021; Klammer et al., 2019a), it continues to serve as a useful heuristic for identifying the contributions of social workers in the stages of problem definition, agenda-setting, policy formulation, policy implementation, and policy evaluation (De Corte & Roose, 2020; Klammer et al., 2019b; McGregor & Millar, 2020).

Studies have demonstrated, for instance, that social workers influence agenda-setting by framing social issues for policymakers (Cohen, 2021; Kindler & Kehl, 2024; Zhang et al., 2021), provide expert input during policy drafting (Gysi, 2021; Ritter, 2026), reinterpret and adapt policies during their implementation (Beltran et al., 2022; Fargion, 2018; Spruill et al., 2022), and lead evaluative efforts to assess policy outcomes (D'Emilione et al., 2019; Weiss-Gal & Gal, 2019).

Taken together, these contributions shed light on social workers' engagement at distinct stages of policymaking. Yet, studies rarely examine how their involvement develops across different stages of a policy process, thereby limiting understanding of the continuity and

change in social workers' involvement over time. Responding to this gap in the current state of research, the present study assumes that, over the course of a policy process, different professional roles may gain prominence and policy strategies may shift. Accordingly, parts of this dissertation analyse the stages of the policy process surrounding the planned reductions in social assistance in the canton of Bern and examine how social workers' policy strategies, roles, and timing intersected within this case.

1.1.4 Factors influencing social workers' policy engagement

A fourth important strand of research examines the factors that influence the forms and levels of social workers' engagement in policy. This line of scholarship has a relatively long tradition, with early studies emerging in the United States during the 1980s and 1990s (e.g. Ezell, 1993; Parker & Sherraden, 1991; Reeser & Epstein, 1990; Wolk, 1981). A considerable number of these studies drew on the Civic Voluntarism Model to explain social workers' policy engagement. They found that resources – such as political skills or knowledge – psychological engagement with politics – including political interest, political efficacy, or party affiliation – and mobilisation networks – such as trade unions, political parties, or professional organisations – are associated with social workers' involvement in policy processes (Hamilton & Fauri, 2001; Kim et al., 2023; Ostrander et al., 2021; Ritter, 2008).

Although widely used, the Civic Voluntarism Model offers only a partial explanation of social workers' policy engagement. Developed within political science to explain civic and political participation across a range of populations (Verba et al., 1995; Schlozman et al., 2018), it privileges micro-level factors and thus understates the influence of organisational and structural contexts. To address these limitations, Gal and Weiss-Gal (2023a) formulated the Policy Engagement Conceptual Framework, which posits that four main factors – individual motivation, organisational facilitation, opportunities within the political system,

and the broader socio-economic and professional environments – shape social workers’ policy engagement.

The first factor, motivation, encompasses micro-level predictors, some of which also appear in the Civic Voluntarism Model. Research at this level is well developed and has demonstrated that factors such as policy skills (Gewirtz-Meydan et al., 2016), professional attitudes (Gilboa & Weiss-Gal, 2022), gender (Meehan, 2018; Ostrander et al., 2023), ethnicity (Darawshy et al., 2021; Nouman et al., 2023), personality traits (Schwartz-Tayri, 2021), personal values (Krips et al., 2024), and education (Berkowitz, 2024; Weiss-Gal & Gal, 2020; Witt et al., 2020) influence social workers’ policy engagement.

The second factor, organisational facilitation, recognises that most social workers are employed within organisations. Their engagement in policy is therefore shaped, at least in part, by the degree of support or discouragement they encounter in their workplace. Prior research has shown that organisational culture, expectations, and explicit support for policy engagement strongly affect social workers’ actual participation in policy-related activities (e.g. Boehm et al., 2018; Gewirtz-Meydan et al., 2016; Nouman et al., 2020).

The third and fourth factors – opportunity and environments – constitute macro-level predictors. Opportunity recognises that individual motivation and supportive organisational cultures translate into strong policy engagement only when the political system offers social workers opportunities to access policy processes (Gal & Weiss-Gal, 2020). Finally, all these dynamics are embedded within broader environments, including the welfare regime, prevailing social problems and policy agendas, and the professional status of social work within society.

Although the Policy Engagement Conceptual Framework provides a comprehensive lens for examining the factors that shape policy engagement, its empirical application remains uneven across the four dimensions. Existing studies have primarily concentrated on motivational and organisational factors, whereas considerably less attention has been given to

how political opportunities and the broader social and professional environments influence social workers' participation in policy processes (Gal & Weiss-Gal, 2020). Addressing this gap, one part of the present dissertation situates social workers' engagement within the Swiss political system and, more specifically, within the policy case concerning proposed reductions in social assistance in the canton of Bern. In doing so, it examines how Switzerland's direct democracy, federalist structure, and consensus system, together with the particular characteristics of the Bern case, shape social workers' policy engagement.

1.1.5 Summary and research gaps

Despite substantial progress in research on social workers' policy engagement, several underexplored areas persist across the four dimensions outlined above. The first strand of research has advanced the discourse by examining the policy strategies employed by social workers. However, this body of work has predominantly relied on quantitative approaches, offering only limited attention to the contextual specificities of these strategies. A second strand has investigated policy engagement through the lens of distinct professional roles, such as team leaders, frontline practitioners, community social workers, and members of parliament. Yet, comparative analyses across different roles remain scarce, leaving largely unexplored whether variations in professional roles correspond to differences in opportunities, strategies, and levels of engagement. A third line of inquiry has focused on social workers' involvement at specific stages of the policymaking process. However, few studies have explored how their engagement evolves across multiple stages of a policy process, which would provide valuable insights into the continuity and transformation of their involvement over time. A fourth dimension of research has identified various motivational and facilitating factors influencing social workers' policy engagement. Nevertheless, despite conceptual advances in this regard, empirical investigations into political opportunities and broader environments remain limited. Finally, existing studies have tended to examine these four dimensions – strategies, roles,

timing, and influencing factors – independently. Consequently, little is known about how these dimensions intersect, or more specifically, about why, how, and when social workers in particular roles adopt specific strategies at different stages of the policy process.

1.2 Research aim and questions

Addressing the gaps in existing scholarship outlined above, this dissertation examined social workers' policy engagement through an in-depth case study of the planned cuts to social assistance in the canton of Bern in Switzerland between 2012 and 2019. By situating the analysis within this concrete political context, the study sought to develop a contextualised understanding of when and how social workers participate in policymaking, the roles they assume, and the political institutions that enable or constrain their engagement. Guided by this empirical foundation, the research was structured around three interrelated questions:

- (1) What are the key political institutions in Switzerland and how do they affect social workers' policy engagement?
- (2) When, and in which roles, do social workers become involved in policy processes?
- (3) What policy engagement strategies do social workers employ?

1.3 Methodology

To address both the broader context of Swiss political institutions and the specific policy engagement of social workers in the Bern case, the research combined conceptual analysis with empirical investigation. More precisely, the paper presented in Chapter 2 analysed how Swiss political institutions affect social workers' opportunities to engage in policy. Building on this, the articles presented in Chapters 3 and 4 empirically explored social workers' concrete involvement in the Bern case, drawing on a reflexive thematic analysis of problem-centred interviews and a comprehensive collection of documents. The following sections outline the study context, procedures of data generation and analysis, strategies employed to ensure analytic rigor, and ethical considerations.

1.3.1 Study context

This dissertation investigated social workers' policy engagement in the context of proposed cuts to social assistance in the canton of Bern between 2012 and 2017. In Switzerland, social assistance functions as a means-tested, last-resort safety net for people living in poverty, covering housing, health, and basic living costs. As one of the largest fields of employment for social workers, the delivery and regulation of social assistance differ significantly across cantons, reflecting the federalist structure and divergent cantonal policy priorities. To address this fragmentation, the Swiss Conference on Social Welfare (SKOS) issues non-binding guidelines intended to harmonize the implementation of social assistance nationwide (Ladner, 2019; Keller, 2025; Madörin et al., 2017).

Despite these coordination efforts, the early 2000s witnessed growing criticism of social assistance from conservative factions. The canton of Bern emerged as a pioneer in this debate when its parliament decided in 2013 to substantially reduce financial benefits for all recipients (Keller, 2025; Parliament Canton Bern, 2012; State Chancellery Canton Bern, 2013). The subsequent policy formulation process between 2013 and 2018 was closely monitored and contested by social workers outside the parliament. Opposition arose from a range of actors, including the social work professional organisation AvenirSocial, frontline practitioners, directors of social services, critical social workers, as well as social work coalitions. These actors, amongst other things, contributed their expertise, organized demonstrations, and engaged in lobbying to influence the policy debate. The process culminated in a referendum launched by social workers and allied actors, which triggered a popular vote in 2019. The electorate ultimately rejected the proposed radical cuts, thereby overturning the parliamentary decision (Moth et al., 2025; Sancar, 2021; Sommer, 2019; Wipf, 2024).

This multi-faceted cantonal process – spanning several stages, involving both parliamentary and extra-parliamentary arenas, and involving diverse social work actors from

professional associations to frontline practitioners – provided a rich empirical basis for analysing social workers’ policy activities in a real-world context. Chapter 3 presents a more detailed account of this case.

1.3.2 Data generation and sample

The analysis of social workers’ policy engagement in the case of the planned reductions in social assistance was based on a dataset consisting of interviews and a comprehensive collection of relevant documents.

The interviewees were recruited through a combination of purposive and snowball sampling (Gobo, 2006; Patton, 2015; Silverman, 2018) according to three inclusion criteria: (a) involvement in the policy process under study, (b) employment as a social worker during the relevant period between 2012 and 2019, and (c) possession of a formal qualification in social work. From June to November 2023, they participated in problem-centred interviews. This method of data generation was chosen because it combines narrative-generating elements with focused prompts, thereby enabling participants to articulate their own experiences while also ensuring that the interviews address theoretically relevant aspects of the research problem (Misoch, 2019; Witzel, 2000; Witzel & Reiter, 2012, 2022). Guided by a thematic protocol, the interviews began with questions on the broader context and development of the policy case, before moving to more specific prompts regarding participants’ involvement in the policy process and the strategies they employed. Interviews were conducted at locations chosen by the participants, lasted between 29 and 107 minutes ($M = 75$ minutes), were audio-recorded, and transcribed verbatim. Oral and written informed consent was obtained from all respondents. To ensure confidentiality, participants are identified through unique numerical pseudonyms (e.g. sw1).

As shown in Table 1, a total of 38 social workers were interviewed, of whom 16 self-identified as female and 22 as male. Their ages ranged from 31 to 67 years, with a mean age

of 47 years. All respondents held a bachelor's (n = 23) or master's degree in social work (n = 15), and their social work experience ranged from 5 to 44 years, with an average of 20 years. Participants were involved in the policy case in various roles, with most serving as directors (n = 13) or frontline social workers in social services (n = 11). Nine of the participants were leaders (president, board member, director) of the Bern Conference of Social Welfare and Child Protection (BKSE), while another six were leaders (director of the national organisation, board member of the cantonal chapter) of the Swiss social work professional organisation (AvenirSocial). Several respondents were active in social movements: five identified as critical social workers, and 18 were involved in the Verkehrt group, a grassroots initiative opposing proposed reductions in social assistance. Additionally, four participants were members of the cantonal parliament. As further detailed in Table 1, many participants held multiple roles simultaneously, for example, sw29 was a social services director, a BKSE leader, and a Verkehrt activist concurrently.

While a range of additional actors, including lawyers, journalists, party officials, and representatives of various associations, contributed to the development of the Bern case, their perspectives and activities were not included in the analysis. This exclusion reflects the study's analytical focus and the predefined inclusion criteria, which centre exclusively on social workers' engagement in the policy process.

Table 1. Overview of the professional and socio-demographic backgrounds of the social workers interviewed for the study

Interviewee	Main role	Additional roles	Gender	Education	SW experience	Age
sw01	AvenirSocial leader	Social services social worker, Verkehrt activist	female	BSW	13	36
sw02	AvenirSocial leader	Social services social worker, Verkehrt activist	female	BSW	11	36
sw03	AvenirSocial leader	Social services social worker, Verkehrt activist	male	MSW	13	40
sw04	AvenirSocial leader	Social services social worker	female	MSW	10	34
sw05	AvenirSocial leader	Verkehrt activist	female	MSW	8	57
sw06	AvenirSocial leader	-	male	MSW	24	47
sw07	BKSE leader	Social services director	male	BSW	31	57
sw08	BKSE leader	Social services director	male	BSW	33	60
sw09	BKSE leader	Social services director	male	BSW	43	67
sw10	Social services director	Critical social worker	female	MSW	10	38
sw11	Social services director	-	male	BSW	24	53
sw12	Social services director	BKSE leader	male	BSW	34	60
sw13	Social services director	BKSE leader	male	BSW	24	57
sw14	Social services director	BKSE leader	male	BSW	25	55
sw15	Social services director	-	male	BSW	24	58
sw16	Social services director	BKSE leader	male	BSW	27	57
sw17	Social services director	-	male	BSW	30	59
sw18	Social services social worker	-	male	BSW	6	34
sw19	Social services social worker	-	male	BSW	24	64
sw20	Social services social worker	-	female	MSW	15	41
sw21	Member of cantonal parliament	-	female	BSW	35	64
sw22	Member of cantonal parliament	Verkehrt activist	male	BSW	33	63
sw23	Member of cantonal parliament	BKSE leader, social services director	female	BSW	25	53
sw24	Member of cantonal parliament	-	female	MSW	17	40
sw25	Verkehrt activist	Critical social worker	female	BSW	14	38
sw26	Verkehrt activist	-	female	BSW	5	31
sw27	Verkehrt activist	Social services social worker, critical social worker	female	BSW	10	36
sw28	Verkehrt activist	Critical SW	male	BSW	6	40
sw29	Verkehrt activist	BKSE leader, social services director	male	MSW	15	45
sw30	Verkehrt activist	Social services social worker	female	MSW	12	35
sw31	Verkehrt activist	-	female	MSW	5	39
sw32	Verkehrt activist	-	male	MSW	10	38
sw33	Verkehrt activist	Social services social worker	male	MSW	12	36
sw34	Verkehrt activist	-	male	MSW	21	44
sw35	Verkehrt activist	-	female	MSW	14	34
sw36	Verkehrt activist	Social services social worker	female	BSW	44	65
sw37	Verkehrt activist	Social services social worker, critical social worker	male	MSW	10	35
sw38	NGO director	-	male	BSW	32	67

Notes. AvenirSocial = The Swiss Social Work Professional Organisation; BKSE = Bern Conference for Social Welfare and Child Protection

To situate interviewees' accounts within the broader policy process of attempted cuts to social assistance, the study complemented interview data with a diverse set of documentary sources. These included public materials (e.g. newspaper clippings, parliamentary minutes, or press releases) as well as non-public materials provided by interviewees (e.g. meeting minutes or archived websites of social work organisations) (Prior, 2003, 2006; Salheiser, 2019). These sources were compiled between June 2023 and June 2025 using snowball and purposive sampling techniques (Gobo, 2006; Patton, 2015; Silverman, 2018). Inclusion required that documents directly pertained to the policy process under investigation (e.g. historical analyses) or were produced as part of that process (e.g. parliamentary minutes or protest documentation). These materials were provided directly by interviewees, identified through web searches, and retrieved via the Swissdox media archive. Through manual screening, an initial set of over 1,600 records was narrowed down by excluding duplicates and materials that did not meet the inclusion criteria.

As shown in Table 2, the final dataset comprised 355 unique documents from 11 publishers. This collection included academic literature, minutes of parliamentary and coalition meetings, governmental reports, websites, leaflets and posters, press documents, and newspaper clippings. In the following, all documents are referred to by unique numerical codes (e.g. d1).

1.3.3 Data analysis

The empirical material underpinning Chapters 3 and 4 was analysed using reflexive thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006, 2019, 2021). This approach was selected for its capacity to generate patterned meaning across heterogeneous qualitative materials and its suitability for examining social workers' roles, strategies, and the timing of their engagement within a complex, multi-year policy process. While the two analyses presented in Chapters 3 and 4 both followed a primarily inductive logic centred on semantic meaning, they differed in analytical focus and data base.

Table 2. *Overview of the publishers, types and numbers of the documents analysed for the study*

Publisher	Type	Number	Documents
Academic literature	Articles, books and reports	14	d1–14
AvenirSocial	Consultation responses	2	d15–16
	Leaflets and posters	4	d17–20
	Press documents	14	d21–34
	Other	5	d35–39
BKSE	Consultation responses	7	d40–46
	Press documents	7	d47–53
	Reports	2	d54–55
	Websites	1	d56
Critical social workers	Websites	8	d57–64
Government	Press documents	36	d65–100
	Reports	4	d101–104
	Resolutions	15	d105–119
Municipalities	Press documents	7	d120–126
Newspapers	Newspaper clippings	145	d127–271
Parliament	Parliamentary minutes	7	d272–278
	Parliamentary regulations	2	d279–280
Referendum Committee	Leaflets and posters	2	d281–282
	Meeting minutes	8	d283–290
	Press documents	1	d291
	Websites	1	d292
	Other	1	d293
Stop the Cut Collective	Leaflets and posters	3	d294–296
	Websites	24	d297–320
Verkehrt	Leaflets and posters	2	d321–322
	Meeting minutes	21	d323–343
	Press documents	5	d344–348
	Websites	2	d349–350
	Other	5	d351–355

The analysis reported in Chapter 3 examined the intersection of social workers’ roles, strategies, and phases of involvement across the policy process and drew on both interview transcripts and documentary materials. By contrast, the analysis presented in Chapter 4 focused exclusively on policy strategies, foregrounding social workers’ own perspectives as articulated in the interview data. In both cases, the analytic process unfolded through six phases, as outlined by Braun and Clarke (2022) and described below. While these phases are presented sequentially, they overlapped in practice, with activities such as refinement and consolidation recurring across stages as part of an iterative analytic process.

Phase 1 – Familiarisation with the dataset. The analytic process began with repeated and immersive engagement with the data. For the analysis reported in Chapter 3, familiarisation comprised all 38 interview transcripts and 355 documentary sources, whereas familiarisation for the analysis presented in Chapter 4 focused exclusively on the interview material. Interview transcripts were read alongside the corresponding audio recordings to attend closely to participants’ emphasis and contextual nuance.

During this phase, initial analytic observations were documented through preliminary notes. These notes captured recurring patterns and points of analytic interest, such as repeated references to emotions in social workers’ policy engagement, both as elements of their strategies and as factors shaping decisions to become involved. Such early reflections informed subsequent analytic decisions regarding the scope and focus of the analysis. For example, although interviewees frequently referred to barriers and facilitators of policy engagement, these aspects were not pursued further, as the analytic focus was deliberately placed on strategies, roles, and timing within the policy process rather than on influencing or motivational factors.

Phase 2 – Coding. In the second phase, systematic inductive coding was conducted using MAXQDA. The entire dataset was coded, and all codes were collated together with their associated data extracts to support subsequent stages of analysis and reporting. Coding was guided by the respective research questions but otherwise remained inductive in nature, as no predefined theoretical framework or deductive codebook was applied.

For the analysis reported in Chapter 3, coding proceeded through three rounds. The first round focused on policy strategies, the second on social workers’ roles, and the third on key events and phases of the policy process. This layered coding approach facilitated the identification of patterns within strategies, roles, and timing, as well as the examination of how these dimensions intersected across the empirical material. Figure 1 illustrates such an

intersection by presenting a data segment in which all three types of codes co-occur. The data segment depicts an AvenirSocial leader describing interactions with politicians during the first parliamentary reading. Documentary materials and interview transcripts were treated uniformly as textual data and analysed in the same manner, reflecting the analysis's focus on semantic meaning.

Figure 1. *Illustrative coded data segment in MAXQDA*

The analysis underpinning Chapter 4 followed the same inductive logic but was more narrowly focused. Drawing exclusively on interview transcripts, coding concentrated on explicit and implicit references to policy strategies employed by participants. In both analyses, the coded data segments varied considerably in length. Coding was conducted at the level of meaning units, understood as continuous segments of text addressing the same action, event, or idea, and extending until a change in content or meaning was identified. On this basis, code labels were assigned to brief phrases (e.g. “distributing leaflets”), short sentences (e.g. “I led the demonstration”), longer paragraphs (see Figure 1), or, in some instances, entire documents, for example when an organisation such as Verkehrt issued a press release.

Phase 3 – Identifying initial patterns. Building on the codes developed in the previous phase, the third phase involved clustering conceptually related codes into broader patterns of meaning. In both analyses, this process was supported by the use of thematic maps created in the Miroboard software. Specifically, all codes generated in MAXQDA were imported as

individual sticky notes into Miroboard, where they could be moved, grouped, and rearranged flexibly.

For the analysis reported in Chapter 3, codes relating to policy strategies, social workers’ roles, and phases of the policy process were initially mapped separately at this stage in order to preserve their distinct analytical foci. This facilitated careful consideration of each dimension before examining their intersections. By contrast, the analysis presented in Chapter 4 focused solely on policy strategies and resulted in an initial thematic map (see Figure 2) that clustered related forms of engagement and tentatively articulated relationships between them. For example, strategies oriented towards service users were provisionally grouped together, while more activist or formal forms of involvement were explored as potentially contrasting policy engagement strategies.

Figure 2. *Initial thematic map of policy strategy clusters*

During this phase, identical or near-identical codes were merged, and code labels were refined to better reflect the evolving analytic focus. Some codes were provisionally set aside in a “not yet assigned” category where they did not appear to meaningfully contribute to addressing the research questions at this stage. This included, for example, codes capturing

interviewees' political ideology or evaluative attitudes towards particular strategies rather than descriptions of their actual engagement.

Phase 4 – Developing themes. The fourth phase focused on refining the initial patterns into coherent and analytically meaningful themes and sub-themes. To develop the themes presented in Chapter 4, the initial thematic map in Figure 2 served as a basis. From this map, theme development unfolded through a series of iterative steps. First, drawing on the provisional cluster labels, the original codes, and their associated data segments, conceptually similar and overlapping clusters were systematically reviewed, rearranged, and, where appropriate, merged into themes. For example, all clusters referring to different forms of service user involvement in policy engagement were brought together under a new theme labelled “involving service users”. Second, individual codes from other clusters were reassessed and reassigned to these developing themes where they provided a better conceptual fit. For instance, the code “informing service users about the public vote” was relocated from the cluster “mobilising and motivating” to the theme “involving service users”. Third, codes and clusters that did not explicitly describe policy strategies were excluded from further analysis. This concerned, for example, instances in which participants qualified their own involvement as insignificant without providing any substantive account of concrete strategic practices. Finally, the remaining themes were further refined by organising their underlying codes into analytically meaningful sub-themes in order to capture distinct facets of each overarching theme. For example, “involving service users” was structured around the sub-themes “informing service users”, “mobilising service users” and “collaborating with service users”.

For the analysis presented in Chapter 3, theme development comprised two overlapping analytic moves. First, themes were developed separately at the levels of strategies, roles and phases, following the same general approach described above for Chapter 4. During this step, for example, different leadership positions within the Bern

policymakers” and its associated sub-themes. Working with this map enabled the further interrogation and reorganisation of themes in relation to other themes and sub-themes across the analytical axes. For instance, initial themes relating to public relations and media interventions were merged into a broader theme encompassing both media and public relations, as these strategies were frequently employed in combination across the entire policy process and by social workers in almost all the identified roles.

Phase 5 – Defining and naming themes. The fifth phase focused on sharpening the scope, boundaries, and internal coherence of the themes developed in the preceding phases. At this stage, no additional modifications were made to the thematic maps. Instead, drawing on the original codes and their associated data segments, each theme was systematically interrogated to clarify and articulate its core meaning. In both analyses, this phase involved two closely interrelated tasks. First, informative and concise names were assigned to each theme to capture its central focus. Where possible, names of themes were chosen at the same level of abstraction and in similar length. For example, the strategies identified in the analysis presented in Chapter 3 were labelled “conducting media and public relations”, “organising protest activities”, “mobilising direct democracy”, “influencing policymakers” and “serving in parliament”. Second, theme definitions were developed to articulate the essence and scope of each theme. For the analysis presented in Chapter 3, this entailed a comprehensive description of the policy process across the identified phases, alongside more concise definitions of social workers’ strategies and roles. By contrast, the analysis underpinning Chapter 4 focused on developing in-depth descriptions of each policy strategy. In some cases, this process of defining and refining themes prompted minor adjustments to theme names to ensure close alignment between names and substantive content.

Phase 6 – Writing up. Finally, the sixth phase centred on writing up the analysis in order to address the research questions. In the analysis presented in Chapter 3, this involved moving

beyond the description of individual themes to demonstrate how social workers' policy strategies evolved over time and varied according to the roles they assumed in the Bern case. The analysis showed, for example, that in early stages of the process insider strategies dominated but were increasingly supplemented and replaced by outsider strategies as the case unfolded. In Chapter 4, the writing process wove together the strategies identified in the interview material and highlighted their interrelations. For example, creating emotional involvement emerged as a cross-cutting approach that informed other strategies, notably efforts to influence both formal policymaking and public opinion. In both analyses, writing was conceived not merely as a mode of reporting but as an integral component of the analytic process, through which interpretations were consolidated, the internal coherence of the themes was critically assessed, and the contribution of the findings to existing scholarship on social workers' policy engagement was discussed. The final write-up incorporated carefully selected illustrative data extracts to anchor the analysis in the empirical material and to demonstrate how interpretations were grounded in participants' accounts and documentary evidence.

1.3.4 Analytic rigor

Unlike other forms of thematic analysis – such as coding reliability thematic analysis (see Boyatzis, 1998) – the quality of reflexive thematic analysis “depends not on notions of consensus, accuracy or reliability, but on immersion, creativity, thoughtfulness and insight.” (Braun & Clarke, 2022, p. 268). Accordingly, and following Braun and Clarke (2022) and Nowell et al. (2017), the following strategies were adopted to ensure the quality and analytic rigor of this study.

Given the size and complexity of the dataset, systematic data management was central to the analytic process. All raw data (interview transcripts and documents) were stored on a secure server, organised into folders by data type, and labelled with unique identifiers. A

spreadsheet provided an overview that linked each document with additional information such as date of creation, file type, title, source, and – in the case of interview transcripts – sociodemographic and professional background information of participants. This structure ensured that raw data were consistently archived and accessible.

An audit trail was maintained to ensure that, although another researcher might not reach identical conclusions, the methodological decision-making process would remain transparent and traceable. All analytic steps and decisions were systematically documented in the form of memos, coding notes and thematic maps using MAXQDA and Miroboard, thereby enabling the reconstruction of analytic choices and the evaluation of interpretive adequacy. In addition, reflexive journaling was employed to capture daily research activities, methodological considerations, and personal reflections, explicitly acknowledging the researcher's role as the 'human instrument' of data analysis (Lincoln & Guba, 1985).

Methodological decisions as well as emerging findings were not developed in isolation but were instead subjected to continuous engagement in a variety of academic face-to-face settings. Throughout the research process, work-in-progress was presented and critically discussed in doctoral seminars, research workshops, and academic conferences. In parallel, regular meetings with doctoral supervisors ensured further guidance and reflection. These exchanges created opportunities to refine methodological choices, interrogate analytical interpretations, and enhance the conceptual clarity of the study. Taken together, these processes of reflexion, discussion, and critique contributed to the transparency, credibility, and rigor of the research.

1.3.5 Ethical considerations

The study received ethical approval from the Paul Baerwald School of Social Work and Social Welfare at the Hebrew University of Jerusalem (approval number 09102022) and complied with the data protection regulations of the Eastern Switzerland University of

Applied Sciences. As outlined earlier, the research relied on three types of data sources, each requiring specific ethical considerations.

First, public documents (e.g. newspaper articles, parliamentary minutes, and websites) were analysed. As these materials were publicly available, consent from their producers was not required. Nevertheless, care was taken to reference them accurately and to present them in context in order to avoid misrepresentation.

Second, internal documents from social work organisations and groups (e.g. meeting minutes and archived websites) were examined. These materials were not publicly available and often contained non-anonymised personal information. Access was granted through organisational representatives, who provided written informed consent for their use after receiving a detailed explanation of the study and participants' rights. Where applicable, individual social workers named in these documents were contacted and asked to provide written informed consent as well.

Third, problem-centred interviews were conducted with social workers. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to data collection. Consistent with the procedure for internal documents, interviewees were informed about the purpose of the study, the voluntary nature of participation, and their right to withdraw at any time without negative consequences.

For the purposes of data analysis and dissemination of the findings, all interview transcripts and documents were pseudonymised. Personal names were replaced with unique numerical identifiers (e.g. sw1). The data were stored on a password-protected server and are scheduled for permanent deletion on 30 June 2031.

1.4 Dissertation outline

Following the introduction in Chapter 1, the dissertation is organised into three main chapters (Chapters 2–4), each based on a standalone article, and concludes with a discussion

of the study's findings in Chapter 5. Together, these chapters seek to develop a contextualised understanding of when and how social workers participate in policymaking, the roles they assume, and the political institutions that enable or constrain their engagement. Each chapter focuses on a distinct research question, while their combination provides a multi-layered understanding of social workers' policy engagement in the case of proposed social assistance cuts in the canton of Bern.

Chapter 2, entitled "Political institutions and social work: How Switzerland's direct democracy, federalist structure, and consensus system affect social workers' policy engagement", adopts a conceptual approach. This article is among the first to explore the link between political institutions and social workers' policy engagement through the lens of a specific political system as a case study. It analyses the key political institutions in Switzerland – direct democracy, federalism, and consensus system – and considers how they affect social workers' opportunities to participate in policy processes, thereby addressing the first research question. This chapter was first published in the *British Journal of Social Work* in September 2023.

Chapter 3, entitled "Social work in the policy process: A case-study on Swiss social workers' roles, strategies, and timing of policy engagement", builds on an empirical investigation of the contested Bern case. Using thematic analysis of interviews and documentary evidence, it closely examines the unfolding of this policy process and explores social workers' participation in it. By focusing on the Bern case, this study provides one of the few in-depth case studies of social workers' real-world policy involvement. The findings demonstrate how the social workers' engagement evolved through a dynamic interplay of roles, strategies, and political timing, thereby addressing the second and third research questions. This chapter was submitted to the *Journal of Social Work* in September 2025 and is currently under review.

Chapter 4, entitled “Social work and policy engagement: A thematic analysis of Swiss social workers’ policy strategies”, further builds on the case study by providing a deeper account of the strategies employed by social workers to influence the policy process in Bern. Based on a thematic analysis of interviews with social workers involved in this case, the findings describe influencing formal policymaking, shaping public opinion, building coalitions, mobilising engagement, creating emotional involvement, contributing professional knowledge, and involving service users as distinct policy strategies, thereby addressing the third research question. This chapter was published in the *European Journal of Social Work* in September 2025.

Chapter 5 integrates the findings of the three articles. It discusses their combined implications for understanding social workers’ roles, strategies, and timing in policy engagement and considers the relevance of the findings for theory, practice, and future research. The chapter also reflects on the methodological choices of this study and situates its contribution within international debates on social workers’ policy engagement.

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CHAPTER 2

Political institutions and social work: How Switzerland's direct democracy, federalist structure, and consensus system affect social workers' policy engagement

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Political institutions and social work: How Switzerland's direct democracy, federalist structure, and consensus system affect social workers' policy engagement

Abstract

The profession of social work has a long tradition of engaging with policy to promote social justice, the well-being of service users, and the working conditions of social workers. Previous studies have mainly focused on the levels and forms of social workers' policy engagement. However, little is known about the factors that influence social workers' decisions to engage in policy. Addressing this research gap, this study focuses on one very specific influencing factor that has so far only received limited scholarly attention, namely, political institutions. More specifically, the article draws upon Switzerland as a case study, and examines how Switzerland's direct democracy, federalist structure, and consensus system promote social workers' policy engagement. The findings illustrate how these three key political institutions provide important opportunities for social workers – as individuals or as members of groups and coalitions – to access formal and informal areas of the policy process, both as private citizens and as part of their job. Based on these findings, the final section of the article outlines suggestions for further research.

Introduction

Social work is closely intertwined with formal and informal policy processes. Accordingly, social workers have a long history of policy engagement, addressing not only individual problems but also initiating social change at the structural level (Jansson, 2018; Lane and Pritzker, 2018; Dischler and Kulke, 2021; Gal and Weiss-Gal, 2023; Leiber et al., 2023). They use their expertise and skills to influence all stages of the policy process, from agenda setting to policy formulation, implementation and evaluation (Klammer et al., 2019). Recognising the importance of policy engagement, the global definition of social work (IASSW and IFSW, 2014), as well as various national codes of ethics (e.g. AvenirSocial, 2010; NASW, 2017; BASW, 2021), defines political intervention as integral to social work. Social workers are not only bureaucrats who implement policies but also agents with the potential to shape policy in multiple ways. Benz and Rieger (2015) identify four dimensions of political social work: implementation, political consulting, lobbying and policy education. Similarly, Gal and Weiss-Gal (2023) distinguish between social workers' policy engagement through civic routes – voluntary political participation and running for or holding elected political office – and their engagement through professional routes – policy practice, academic policy practice, policy involvement by professional organisations and street-level policy involvement (Gal and Weiss-Gal, 2015; Weiss-Gal, 2017a). Whilst there is some research on the levels and forms of policy engagement by social workers, little is known about the factors that influence their willingness and decisions to engage in it (Weiss-Gal, 2016).

Addressing this gap, this article focuses on political institutions, which is one of the factors that has received limited scholarly attention so far. Political institutions are ‘. . . collections of structures, rules, and standard operating procedures that have a partly autonomous role in political life’ (March and Olsen, 2008, p. 4). They typically include such

elements as the structure of the parliament, the degree of federalism or the extent of direct democratic instruments that together constitute the institutional setting of a given political system or a specific welfare regime. Based on this understanding, this article examines the unique political institutions in Switzerland. The Swiss case serves as an ideal–typical touchstone (Seawright and Gerring, 2008) of a highly developed liberal democracy (Papada et al., 2023) with pronounced direct democratic instruments, federal structure and consensus system. The close study of this particular institutional setting allows for comparisons with similar cases (e.g. countries with strong direct democracy) and contrasts with divergent countries (e.g. unitary states). In the following, this article seeks to describe the key political institutions that comprise Switzerland’s political system and then illustrate how these institutions offer opportunities for social workers to participate in the policy process.

Theoretical background

Previous studies of social workers’ policy engagement have examined how they influence policymaking processes as elected politicians (e.g. Lane and Humphreys, 2011; Gwilym, 2017; Meehan, 2018; McLaughlin et al., 2019; Miller et al., 2021; Binder and Weiss-Gal, 2022; Kindler and Amann, 2022a; Pence and Kaiser, 2023; Demircali et al., 2024; Leitner and Stolz, 2023; Löffler, 2023), through voluntary political participation (e.g. Rome and Hoechstetter, 2010; Lane et al., 2018; Ostrander et al., 2018, 2021; Kindler and Kulke, 2022); as part of their jobs (e.g. Gewirtz- Meydan et al., 2016; Weiss-Gal and Gal, 2020; Gilboa and Weiss-Gal, 2022; Carrilho and Branco, 2023), including academic policy practice (e.g. Gal and Weiss-Gal, 2017; Köngeter et al., 2018); by and through professional organisations (e.g. Hartnett et al., 2005; Scanlon et al., 2006; Beimers, 2015; Guidi, 2020); and as street-level policy entrepreneurs (e.g. Cohen, 2021; Zhang et al., 2021). This research shows that social workers are more involved in politics than are members of the general population, especially in conventional forms of participation such as voting (Hamilton, 1998).

However, social workers tend to engage in activities that require little time, energy or resources (Ostrander et al., 2018), and they are mostly involved in professional activities related to programmes within their organisations, as opposed to influencing policy at the local, state, national or international levels (Weiss-Gal et al., 2020).

Whilst early policy engagement studies tended to focus solely on the extent of social workers' policy involvement (Epstein, 1981; Koeske et al., 2005; Weiss-Gal, 2008), scholarship on the factors associated with their level of engagement (Ritter, 2008; Weiss-Gal et al., 2017; Schwartz-Tayri, 2020) remains limited. To address this gap, Gal and Weiss-Gal (2015, 2023) offer the Policy Engagement (PE) conceptual framework as a tool to better understand why and how social workers engage in policy. This framework claims that social workers' policy engagement is influenced by the environments, motivation, facilitation and opportunity. The following sections briefly introduce these four factors.

Environments

Like social workers' professional practice on the individual, group or community level, their involvement in policy is framed by specific real-world contexts and environments. A first such environment is the welfare regime. In a developed welfare state, social workers will tend to be more fully integrated into established welfare systems that can provide them with opportunities to influence policy, and indeed they may hold formal policy roles within state institutions that enable them to participate in policy processes (Gal and Weiss-Gal, 2023). In addition, the PE framework asserts that problems and policies – more specifically, the severity of societal issues affecting service users, the emergence of new social problems and the deliberations about policies to address (or ignore) them – influence social workers' motivation to engage in policy. In addition, social workers' readiness to engage in policy can also be affected by service users who share their experiences of the absence, limitations or dysfunctions of policies. Social workers'

responses in such situations include not only advocating on behalf of service users, but also empowering them to engage in policy efforts, or working with them to bring about policy change. Finally, social workers' policy engagement depends on the status of the social work profession, its aims (e.g. advocating for a socially just society), the education system and the professional discourse within and beyond professional associations of social work. In sum, all these environments – the welfare regime, policies and problems, service users and the profession – influence social workers' motivation, organisational facilitation and opportunities to affect policy.

Motivation

Scholarship on individual factors motivating social workers' involvement in policy is well advanced (e.g. Hamilton and Fauri, 2001; Ritter, 2008). Many studies of the micro-level of social workers' policy engagement employed the Civic Voluntarism Model (CVM) introduced by Verba et al. (1995). Although originally developed to explain voluntary political participation, scholars have also applied it to predict social workers' policy practice in the course of their jobs (Weiss-Gal and Gal, 2020). These studies found that individual resources; psychological engagement with politics; and membership in recruitment networks, such as professional associations, political parties and trade unions, affect social workers' levels and forms of policy engagement. Whilst the CVM provides some valuable insights into the factors affecting social workers' policy activity and remains popular in the literature, it has its limitations, particularly in explaining social workers' on-the-job activities. A number of studies have identified additional influencing factors at the individual micro-level, such as personal values and professional attitudes (Ezell, 1994; Gilboa and Weiss-Gal, 2022), institution-based factors (Epstein, 1981; Rome and Hoechstetter, 2010; Makaros et al., 2020), personality traits (Schwartz- Tayri, 2020), gender (Meehan, 2018; Ostrander et al., 2023) and ethnicity (Darawshy et al., 2021; Nouman and Azaiza, 2022).

Facilitation

Along with the environments and motivation, facilitation features prominently in the PE framework. This meso-level factor considers that most social workers act as employees within organisations. This means that favourable environments and high personal motivation might not fully explain the policy activity of social workers, especially in the course of doing their jobs. Social workers' levels and forms of policy engagement are strongly affected by the support (or discouragement) that they receive from their place of employment. For example, the organisational culture affecting policy engagement differs significantly between different types of organisations, that is advocacy organisations, non-profit social service providers, government administration or for-profit private practice organisations (Kulke and Schmidt, 2019; Gal and Weiss-Gal, 2023). There is a fairly extensive body of research on facilitation factors, too: organisational (Gewirtz-Meydan et al., 2016; Weiss-Gal and Gal, 2020) and management support for (Boehm et al., 2018), and expectations of (Nouman et al., 2019), policy engagement significantly impacts social workers actual involvement in it.

Opportunity

Social workers' policy engagement is affected by the environments, motivation and facilitation. Complementing these three factors, the PE framework includes 'opportunity' as a fourth variable. Favourable environments, individual motivation and facilitating employers will only lead to strong policy engagement by social workers if they are also given opportunities to access the policymaking process. The extent to which social workers have the opportunity (or not) to access such processes depends – in addition to temporal factors, such as political and policy windows (Kingdon, 2014 [1984]) – on political institutions. As defined above, political institutions in a given context constitute a specific institutional setting, shape the political system of a particular country and strongly influence not only the social welfare system in general but also social workers opportunities to participate in the

policy process. Previous research in this field has examined how social workers use political and policy windows to access policy formulation processes (Branco, 2019) or how they seek to improve their opportunities on all political levels (Nothdurfter and Hermans, 2018; Aviv et al., 2021).

Research gap and purpose of the article

Whilst social workers have always been engaged in policy, research on this particular type of practice is still nascent (Weiss-Gal, 2016, 2017b). Early scholarship focused almost exclusively on the levels and forms of social workers' policy engagement. More recent studies have examined the variables affecting policy activity by social workers. The most recent contribution to this evolving field is the PE framework described above. It identifies the environments, motivation, facilitation and opportunity as the main factors influencing social workers' policy engagement. Whilst studies on environmental, motivational and facilitating factors are well advanced, research on opportunities and access to the policy process is scarce. In particular, the relationship between institutional structures, norms and procedures and social workers' policy engagement remains underexplored. This article tackles this lacuna by focusing on the distinctive political institutions in Switzerland and asks: What are the key political institutions in Switzerland and how do they offer social workers opportunities to participate in the policy process?

Swiss political institutions and their effect on social workers' policy engagement

In Switzerland, most social workers are employed in private organisations (35 per cent). Others work in associations (31 per cent), foundations (20 per cent) or public agencies at the national, cantonal or local levels (14 per cent). Approximately 5 per cent of all social workers are members of the professional association of social work (AvenirSocial, 2018). Furthermore, the interests of service users and social workers are represented by many sector-specific umbrella associations, such as the Swiss Conference of Welfare Organisations

(SKOS). Both AvenirSocial and many of the sector-specific associations actively encourage social workers to participate in policymaking.

Indeed, Switzerland's distinctive political system offers residents, citizens, organisations and professionals – such as social workers – a wide variety of participation opportunities. These result from the unique combination of three key political institutions: semi-direct democracy, federalism and the consensus system (Ladner, 2019; Vatter, 2020). In international comparison, the Swiss political system has been described as a model of direct democracy (Linder and Mueller, 2021), an archetype of federalism (Vatter, 2018) and the clearest prototype of consensus democracy (Lijphart, 2012). The following sections describe the Swiss configuration of these political institutions in more detail and provide examples of how they offer social workers opportunities to participate in the policy process.

Semi-direct democracy

In no other country are ordinary citizens asked to vote on specific policy issues, in addition to voting for their representatives in parliament and government, as often as in Switzerland. Between 1848 and 2022, Swiss citizens voted on 635 policy proposals at the national level (Schaub and Bühlmann, 2022; Swissvotes, 2022), which corresponds to an average of 3.7 votes per year. Whilst other countries also have some direct democratic instruments, Switzerland is the only country that applies them at all federal levels (national, cantonal and local) (Linder and Iff, 2011). The Swiss direct democratic instruments are the popular initiative, the obligatory referendum and the optional referendum.

A popular initiative allows interest groups to propose an amendment to the constitution and/or the revision or repeal of an existing article of the constitution by collecting 100,000 signatures from Swiss citizens. The proposal is then submitted to the people, who accept or reject it by a double majority. This means that both a majority of the citizens and of the cantons must vote in favour of the initiative in order for it to be approved. Similarly,

constitutional amendments and international treaties passed by the parliament require an obligatory/constitutional referendum. Here, too, the policy change only passes if it receives a double majority. Finally, most parliamentary acts are subject to an optional/ legislative referendum, by which they become law unless 50,000 citizens initiate a referendum within 100 days. In the case of a popular vote, a simple majority can approve or reject the bill, notwithstanding the wishes of the cantons. Given the (potential) involvement of both the parliament and the people in policy formulation, the Swiss system is a semi-direct democracy (Linder and Mueller, 2021). Complementing these national-level tools, the cantons and municipalities offer further direct democratic instruments (Sager et al., 2017).

Swiss semi-direct democracy offers social workers opportunities to participate in the policy process both as private citizens and as part of their jobs. Indeed, social workers affect policy at the local, cantonal and national levels (Kehl, 2023), and they are more engaged in politics than are members of the general population. For example, whilst 93 per cent of Swiss social workers vote in national elections, only 48 per cent of Swiss citizens do (Kindler and Amann, 2022b). One important example of social workers' engagement in direct democratic processes is their prominent involvement in a referendum against welfare retrenchment in the canton of Bern. A proposal passed by the cantonal parliament in 2012 sought to cut social welfare benefits for all recipients by 10 per cent (Parliament Bern, 2012, 2013, 2018). After the government's final draft was accepted by a majority in the parliament in 2018, a broad coalition formed to reject this legislation by requiring the holding of a referendum on the issue. This campaign – founded and led by the professional association of social work, field-specific social work associations, directors and staff of social welfare offices, individual social workers and service users – collected sufficient signatures to hold a referendum on the issue (Sancar, 2021). After an extended political and public debate, the process concluded in 2019, when canton citizens voted against reducing social welfare (State Chancellery Bern, 2019).

Federalist structure

The Swiss cantons occupy a central position within the federal state. They all have their own constitutions; executive, legislative and judicial bodies; and multiple ways to influence policy at the national level. Switzerland is therefore considered a model federal state (Watts, 2008). Switzerland's federalist structure includes national, cantonal and local levels. New public tasks are constitutionally assigned to the cantonal level. New services can only be assigned to the national level by amending the national constitution, which requires a majority of both the citizens and the cantons ('double majority') in a popular vote. The twenty-six cantons decide which tasks fall within the competence of the more than 2,100 municipalities (BFS, 2022). The distribution and allocation of responsibilities follows the constitutional principle of subsidiarity, which suggests that tasks should only be transferred to the next highest level if they cannot be handled efficiently at the lower state level (Sager et al., 2017). Municipalities are typically responsible for matters such as local public transportation. Cantons, amongst others, oversee social welfare, whilst the national state deals with broader issues such as social insurance. In many cases, such as social welfare, laws are formulated at the cantonal level, but implemented by local authorities, a process known as executive federalism (Linder and Mueller, 2017; Ladner, 2019).

This approach requires close coordination between all parties, in particular between the cantons and the national state, which are the most relevant actors in policy formulation. In Switzerland, this is done both vertically and horizontally. Vertically, the cantons have two main avenues to influence policy. First, the double majority rule for popular votes on constitutional change gives the cantons some influence over direct democratic decision-making. Secondly, the Council of States, as the second chamber of the parliament, represents the cantons nationally. It consists of two members per canton and one member per semi-canton and possesses the same powers as the first chamber, the National Council (Mueller and

Vatter, 2020). Horizontally, the cantons and municipalities maintain close relations by signing bilateral and multilateral treaties and by meeting in defined groups (e.g. meetings of all cantonal government members responsible for social welfare, SODK) (Sager et al., 2017).

The Swiss federalist structure offers social workers opportunities to participate in the policy process both as private citizens and as part of their jobs. Indeed, social workers do engage in the above-described vertical and horizontal ways of Swiss federalism (Kehl, 2023). One strategy for social workers to do so is to run for or hold elected office (Amann and Kindler, 2021, 2022). Another way is to contribute their expertise as employees of local and cantonal authorities (AvenirSocial, 2018) in policy collaborations between the cantons and/or municipalities. One important example of such a horizontal collaboration is the SKOS, an organisation that focuses on social welfare. Social welfare supplements the regular social insurance benefits, such as unemployment insurance, and is the last-resort safety net provided by the state. In the absence of a national law, social welfare is regulated by the cantons and is implemented in most cases by the municipalities. As a result, the organisation and implementation vary considerably between cantons and municipalities (Schnegg and Matter, 2010; BSV, 2016). Since 1963, the SKOS has addressed this issue by publishing guidelines for social welfare. These guidelines are recommendations for social welfare offices and are not legally binding, except where they are recognised by cantonal law (which is the case in seventeen out of twenty-six cantons, see SKOS, 2022). The members of the SKOS are the federal authorities, the cantons, most municipalities and many private welfare organisations, such as the professional association of social work. Social workers, usually in their roles as representatives of local and cantonal authorities, play an important role in the SKOS and are represented on the board of directors (five out of eleven board members are social workers), the four commissions (twenty-nine out of fifty-one), the strategic board (twenty-one out of forty-nine) and as staff in the head office (three out of ten) (figures as of

August 2023, calculated based on SKOS, n.d.). Thus, social workers influence SKOS strategies, and thereby the development of social welfare policies in Switzerland (SKOS, 2019a, 2019b).

Consensus system

Influenced by the direct democratic instruments and the federalist structure described above, the Swiss political system has developed a consensus democracy, contrasting with the Westminster model of majoritarian democracy (Lijphart, 2012). Its three main features are governing coalitions at all political levels that composed of the main political parties, the cooperation of these parties in the parliaments and the involvement of relevant actors before, during and after the parliamentary phase of the policy process (Linder and Mueller, 2021).

At the national level, the government ('Federal Council') consists of seven federal councillors with equal rights. They come from the four largest parties in the parliament and, according to formal and informal rules, also represent the country's regional, linguistic and gender diversity. The president changes every year on a rotating system and chairs the council, but has only a symbolic role (Linder and Iff, 2011). As in the government, the four largest parties – the Swiss People's Party, the Liberals, the Centre and the Social Democrats, which together represent more than 70 per cent of the electorate (Federal Chancellery, 2022) – also cooperate in parliament via shifting, issue-specific coalitions. This approach aims to formulate legislative compromises that are strong enough to succeed in a potential referendum. To achieve this, consensus is sought not only amongst political parties but also amongst actors outside of the parliamentary system. The political decision-making process therefore involves a variety of actors, including interest groups such as associations, NGOs, etc. (Guy-Ecabert, 2019). These actors can threaten a referendum in order to gain power and can influence at all stages of the policy formulation process (Linder and Iff, 2011; Klammer et al., 2019). In addition, many interest groups, such as coalitions of social service providers or

cantonal authorities, will later be tasked with implementing the adopted policies, thereby contributing to policymaking at the street level.

The Swiss consensus system offers social workers opportunities to participate in the policy process. Indeed, social workers do engage in consensus-seeking bodies, such as extra-parliamentary commissions, pre-parliamentary consultations or roundtables (Federal Council, 2022; Kehl, 2023). To harness the necessary bargaining power, they usually do so collectively, as members of NGOs and associations, and thus as part of their jobs. One important example of social workers' engagement in such consensus seeking is the involvement of the professional association of social workers, AvenirSocial, in the reform of the law on social welfare in the canton of Basel-Landschaft (Grob, 2023). As in the case of Bern, a proposal passed by the cantonal parliament in 2018 aimed to cut social welfare benefits for all recipients by 30 per cent, whilst allowing the so-called 'motivated' service users to improve their financial situation according to a step-by-step plan (Parliament Basel-Landschaft, 2017). AvenirSocial joined forces with five major social welfare NGOs to fight against this (AvenirSocial, 2020). As part of this broad coalition, AvenirSocial's executive directors wrote consultation responses and press releases and helped create a citizens' movement (Verkehrt Basel- Landschaft, n.d.). In the wake of these activities, a first draft proposed by the cantonal government in 2020 had to be heavily revised. Eventually, a less radical version was submitted to parliament in 2021 (Government Basel-Landschaft, 2021a, 2021b). There, too, AvenirSocial and its coalition partners used their expertise and contacts to lobby the members of the parliament. AvenirSocial was even invited to speak before the parliamentary commission in charge and tried to convince as many politicians as possible to vote against the reform (Grob, 2023). This strategy was successful, as, in the final parliamentary vote, the policy change, although approved by a majority, did not reach the threshold of 80 per cent and was therefore subject to a popular vote (Parliament Basel-

Landschaft, 2021). The process concluded in 2022 when a majority of the canton's citizens agreed with the proposed policy changes (Canton Basel- Landschaft, 2022). Although, ultimately, the cut was not fully prevented, this case demonstrates how social work organisations can successfully influence policy as extra-parliamentary actors in the Swiss consensus system.

Conclusions

Globally, social workers have always influenced policies to advance the well-being of service users, the working conditions of social workers and social justice for all. However, previous studies have identified pronounced variations in social workers' levels and forms of policy engagement both across and within countries, fields of practice and types of social welfare organisations (Gal and Weiss-Gal, 2013). These differences result not only from different macro-environmental, meso-workplace and individual-motivational factors but also from the specific configurations of political institutions. Based on this assumption, this article has examined the link between social workers' policy engagement and the following three key political institutions in Switzerland: semi-direct democracy, federalist structure and the consensus system. It has been shown above how these three key political institutions enable social workers to formally and informally influence policymaking, both as private citizens and as part of their jobs.

The institution of semi-direct democracy offers social workers opportunities to participate in the policy process. More specifically, direct democratic tools can be used by individual social workers, professional organisations or coalitions – as in the case of the canton of Bern described above – to challenge unjust laws, to prevent the implementation of harmful policies or to innovate for social change. Whilst the popular initiative generates policy innovation, the obligatory and the optional referendum moderates it, by allowing people to challenge parliamentary decisions (Linder and Mueller, 2021). Additionally, the

institution of federalism, with its intertwined political bodies at different levels, provides opportunities for social workers to participate in the policy process. One way to do so is to run for or hold elected office. Running for office at the local or cantonal level is relatively accessible and can provide ‘political novices’ with initial experience in the political arena. Another way for social workers to influence policy is by contributing their expertise as employees of local and cantonal authorities or organisations, for example in the above-described SKOS. Finally, the institution of consensus democracy offers social workers opportunities to engage in the policy process. Framed by this third political institution, social workers also participate in more formalised, extra-parliamentary consensus-seeking bodies, such as in the mentioned reform process in the canton of Basel- Landschaft. In these bodies, diverse actors with competing goals work to reach compromises on specific policies. Unlike direct democracy and federalism, the consensus system mainly involves social workers in their professional roles. They usually participate in these consensus deliberations as collective actors – for example as representatives or employees of NGOs and associations.

Whilst this article specifically examines the opportunities that semidirect democracy, federalist structure and consensus system offer to participate in policy, these three political institutions and their various intersections can also limit social workers’ access to and influence on the policy process. This is particularly the case when social workers focus mainly on direct democratic instruments to influence policy. Indeed, the Swiss consensus system provides incentives for parliaments and governments – acting in close consultation with relevant extra-parliamentary actors – to reach broad legislative compromises supported by a coalition of powerful interest groups, thus preventing the use of popular initiatives or optional referendums from the outset (Guy-Ecabert, 2019; Ladner, 2019). This was the case, for example, with a recent policy reform in the canton of Aargau, where, against the recommendations of social work organisations such as the Independent Social Welfare Law

Centre (2023), the parliament passed a bill introducing the possibility of hiring private investigators to closely monitor welfare recipients (Parliament Aargau, 2023).

This study is the first to explore the link between political institutions and social workers' policy engagement using a specific political system as a case study. Although the Swiss case is certainly unique, we have shown that political institutions do indeed have the potential to affect social workers opportunities to participate in the policy process. This article therefore fits well into the existing international policy practice discourse, where political institutions remain an understudied variable. Against this background, this article can encourage and guide the systematic exploration of political institutions and their impact on social workers' policy engagement in other national settings. On the one hand, the findings of this article can be theoretically transferred and empirically tested in similar contexts. For example, at the state level, in the USA and in Switzerland, 'the instruments of the referendum and the popular initiative are practically the same, and one can find many similarities in their use. For an assessment of direct democracy, it may thus be most useful to compare their experiences' (Linder and Mueller, 2021, p. 213). On the other hand, contrasting cases will enhance our understanding of how political institutions influence social workers' policy engagement: what routes of policy practice do social workers choose, for example, in a country with fewer (or no) tools of direct democracy? To identify such similar, but also contrasting cases, further research could draw on existing typologies (e.g. Lijphart, 2012) and indices (e.g. the Liberal Democracy Index and its component indices, see Papada et al., 2023). More generally, whilst this article has identified how political institutions provide social workers with access to the policy process, further research should examine the impact of social workers' participation. Finally, the three cases presented above suggest that political institutions influence not only the level of social workers' policy engagement but also whether they participate as citizens or professionals. Therefore, further research should

examine how and under what conditions social workers choose the civic and/or professional route, and how these routes are related.

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CHAPTER 3

Social work in the policy process: A Swiss case-study on the roles, strategies, and timing of social workers' policy engagement

Status: under review

Social work in the policy process: A Swiss case-study on the roles, strategies, and timing of social workers' policy engagement

Abstract

Summary: This article investigates how social workers engaged in the policy process regarding proposed cuts to social assistance in the Swiss canton of Bern between 2012 and 2019. Building on prior scholarship that has typically examined strategies, roles, or timing in isolation, this study explores their intersections. Drawing on 38 problem-centred interviews and 355 policy documents, a thematic analysis reconstructed the policy process, identified the roles and strategies of social workers, and mapped their interplay across distinct phases of the case.

Findings: The analysis revealed four phases of the policy process: agenda-setting, policy formulation, parliamentary decision, and direct-democratic decision. Social workers participated in seven roles (e.g. professional association leaders, service directors, parliamentarians, activists) and employed five main strategies, which clustered into insider approaches (influencing policymakers, serving in parliament) and outsider approaches (media and public relations, protesting, mobilizing direct democracy). While media and public relations were used consistently across roles and phases, the application of other strategies shifted in response to changing political dynamics. Moreover, the configurations of roles influenced strategy choices: those in formal roles, such as service directors, tended to adopt insider approaches, whereas those in informal roles more frequently pursued outsider tactics.

Application: This study advances scholarship on social workers' policy engagement by providing one of the few in-depth case studies of real-world policy involvement. The findings demonstrate how social workers' engagement evolved through a dynamic interplay of roles, strategies, and political timing, underscoring the need for further research into the complex relationship between social work and policymaking.

Introduction

In their work with individuals, groups, and communities, social workers often observe that challenges perceived as individual or group-related are deeply rooted in broader social issues. Policy engagement – defined as the deliberate effort to influence the development, implementation, or evaluation of public policies – allows social workers to address these structural causes rather than merely mitigating their symptoms. This policy orientation is explicitly affirmed in the commentary notes to the global definition of social work, which identify policy formulation, policy analysis, advocacy, and political interventions as core components of social work practice (IASSW & IFSW, 2014). In recent years, a growing body of theoretical scholarship has elaborated on the interdependence between social work and public policy (e.g. Benz & Rieger, 2015; Burzlaff, 2022; Gal & Weiss-Gal, 2023a; Jansson, 2018; Lane & Pritzker, 2018). Complementing these conceptual foundations, empirical studies have begun to examine the specific strategies, temporal dimensions, and diverse roles through which social workers participate in policymaking (Gal & Weiss-Gal, 2023a, 2023b).

Social workers' policy strategies can be categorized as insider or outsider strategies (Cailleux, 2025; De Corte & Roose, 2020). Insider strategies involve direct contact with policymakers through both formal and informal channels. Examples include contacting politicians, networking, lobbying, providing evidence, and presenting testimony to parliamentary committees (Dauti & Bejko, 2025; Gal & Weiss-Gal, 2025; Kindler & Amann, 2022). In contrast, outsider strategies aim to influence decision-makers indirectly by raising public awareness. These strategies can be non-conflictual (e.g. engaging the media) or conflictual (e.g. organizing protests). Empirical findings consistently indicate that social workers tend to favor collaborative and consensus-oriented approaches over more adversarial tactics (Dauti & Bejko, 2024; Gal & Weiss-Gal, 2023b; Gilboa & Weiss-Gal, 2022; Guidi et

al., 2025). While such studies illuminate the forms and range of strategies, they seldom consider the specific stages of the policy process at which these strategies are employed.

Recent scholarship has begun to address this gap by utilizing the policy cycle framework. Although the policy cycle has faced criticism for oversimplifying the iterative and non-linear nature of policymaking (e.g. Benz & Rieger, 2015; Cairney, 2020; Hoefler, 2021), it remains widely used as a heuristic to position social workers' interventions across agenda-setting, policy formulation, implementation, and evaluation (De Corte & Roose, 2020; Klammer et al., 2019; McGregor & Millar, 2020). For instance, studies show that social workers shape agenda-setting processes by framing social problems for policymakers (Cohen, 2021; Kindler & Kehl, 2024; Zhang et al., 2021), contribute professional expertise during policy drafting (Gysi, 2021; Ritter, 2026), reinterpret policy during implementation (Beltran et al., 2022; Fargion, 2018; Spruill et al., 2022), and lead evaluative efforts that assess outcomes (D'Emilione et al., 2019; Weiss-Gal & Gal, 2019). Collectively, these studies examine social workers' engagement in distinct phases but rarely explore how their strategies unfold across multiple stages of the policy process.

In addition to analyses of strategy and timing, a growing body of literature has described the diverse roles through which social workers engage in policy change: as frontline practitioners (Burzlaff et al., 2025; Carvalho et al., 2025; Guidi et al., 2025; Tayeb Elmakias, 2025), team managers (Tzadiki & Weiss-Gal, 2021), heads of social services (Weiss-Gal & Gal, 2025), leaders in social work professional organisations (Guidi, 2020, 2025; Hartnett et al., 2005), social work faculty (Gal & Weiss-Gal, 2017), elected officials (Hallam & Mendes, 2025; Leitner & Stolz, 2023; Löffler, 2024; Kindler et al., 2025), or citizens (Kim et al., 2023; Kindler & Ostrander, 2022; Ostrander et al., 2021).

While prior studies have examined social workers' strategies, their timing within the policy process, and the roles through which they engage, these dimensions have largely been

analyzed separately. Consequently, little is known about how social workers in specific roles adopt particular strategies at different stages of the policy cycle. Addressing this gap, the aim of this study was to gain a better understanding of the intersection of strategies, timing, and roles in social workers' policy engagement. Its overarching research question was: when, how, and in what roles do social workers engage in policy processes? To answer this, the study utilized the real-world case of proposed reductions in social assistance in the canton of Bern, Switzerland, between 2012 and 2019 – a case that encompassed multiple stages of the policy cycle and in which social workers were actively engaged in various roles (Kindler, 2025; Moth et al., 2024). Drawing on this empirical context, four interrelated sub-questions were addressed: (1) How did this policy process unfold? (2) In which roles were social workers involved? (3) What strategies did they employ? (4) During which phases and in which roles did they use these strategies? Given the exploratory and inductive nature of the study, a qualitative approach was adopted to examine social workers' involvement in this policy process.

Methods

Data generation

Ethical approval was obtained from the Ethics Committee of the Paul Baerwald School of Social Work and Social Welfare at the Hebrew University of Jerusalem before data collection began. The dataset addressing the research questions was compiled from interviews and a comprehensive collection of documents.

Interviewees were recruited through a combination of purposive and snowball sampling based on three criteria: involvement in the policy process under study, employment as a social worker during that period, and possession of a formal social work qualification. Between June and November 2023, participants engaged in problem-centered interviews (Witzel & Reiter, 2012). These interviews began with questions about the broader context and development of the policy case before focusing on respondents' roles, timing, and strategies of policy engagement.

Each interview was conducted at a location chosen by the participant, lasted between 29 and 107 minutes (M = 75 minutes), was audio-recorded, and subsequently transcribed verbatim. All respondents provided oral and written informed consent; to preserve confidentiality, they are referred to by unique numerical pseudonyms (e.g. sw1). In total, 38 social workers were interviewed: 16 self-identified as female and 22 as male, with ages ranging from 31 to 67 years. All respondents held a bachelor's (n = 23) or master's degree in social work (n = 15), and their social work experience ranged from 5 to 44 years. Participants were involved in the policy case in various roles, with most serving as directors (n = 13) or frontline social workers in social services (n = 11). Nine of the participants were leaders (president, board member, director) of the Bern Conference of Social Welfare and Child Protection (BKSE), while another six were leaders (director of the national organisation, board member of the cantonal chapter) of the Swiss social work professional organisation (AvenirSocial). Several respondents were active in social movements: five identified as critical social workers, and 18 were involved in the Verkehrt group, a grassroots initiative opposing proposed reductions in social assistance. Additionally, four participants were members of the cantonal parliament. As detailed in the supplementary materials, many participants held multiple roles simultaneously, for example, sw29 was a social services director, a BKSE leader, and a Verkehrt activist concurrently.

To complement the interview data, the study incorporated a wide range of relevant documents. These sources were compiled between June 2023 and June 2025 using snowball and purposive sampling techniques. Inclusion required that documents directly pertained to the policy process under investigation (e.g. historical analyses) or were produced as part of that process (e.g. parliamentary minutes or protest documentation). These materials were provided directly by interviewees, identified through targeted web searches, and retrieved via the Swissdox media archive. Through manual screening, an initial set of over 1,600 records was narrowed down by excluding duplicates and materials that did not meet the inclusion

criteria. The final dataset comprised 355 unique documents from 11 publishers. As detailed in the supplementary materials, this collection included academic literature, minutes of parliamentary and coalition meetings, governmental reports, websites, leaflets and posters, press documents, and newspaper clippings. In the following sections, all documents are referred to by unique numerical codes (e.g. d1).

Data analysis

A thematic analysis, as outlined by Braun and Clarke (2022), was employed to identify themes and patterns across the entire dataset, which included both interview transcripts and documents. The analysis progressed through four inductive and iterative coding stages.

First, the material was coded to construct a detailed timeline of the policy process, delineating its main phases and key events, such as the direct-democratic decision phase. Second, the data were examined to identify the various roles assumed by social workers during the policy process, for example, the role of social services director. Third, all material was coded for instances of policy strategies employed by social workers to influence decision-making, such as conducting media and public relations.

In the fourth stage, the temporal framework developed in the first stage was overlaid with the roles and strategies identified in the subsequent stages. This step allowed for systematic mapping of when, how, and in what roles social workers engaged during the different phases of the policy process. The analysis was supported by qualitative data analysis software, MAXQDA 24, and validated through reflexive journaling, feedback received at scientific conferences, and regular discussions with peer researchers.

Findings

The analysis divided the policy process into four phases: agenda-setting, policy formulation, parliamentary decision, and direct-democratic decision. It identified seven roles and five main policy strategies through which social workers participated in these phases. As

summarized in Table 1, social workers engaged in roles as AvenirSocial leaders, BKSE leaders, critical social workers, members of parliament, social services directors, social services social workers, and Verkehrt activists. They utilized these roles to influence policymakers, organize protest activities, mobilize direct democracy, conduct media and public relations, and serve in parliament. The following sections are structured around the four identified phases to describe the evolution of this policy case and examine social workers' engagement in it.

Agenda-setting

Social assistance serves as Switzerland's last safety net for individuals in poverty, providing housing, health-related costs, a basic subsistence allowance, and additional situation-specific benefits. Due to Switzerland's federalist system, social assistance is regulated at the cantonal level, with coordination by the Swiss Conference on Social Welfare (SKOS), which issues non-binding guidelines to harmonize social assistance across all 26 cantons (d2, d8).

Since the early 2000s, SKOS and social assistance in general have faced increasing political attacks, particularly from conservative and right-wing parties that have framed welfare recipients as undeserving or fraudulent while promoting an agenda focused on reducing benefits. Led by the right-wing Swiss People's Party, 17 cantonal parliaments debated measures such as stricter sanctions and lower benefit levels between 2013 and 2015, with these debates amplified by critical media coverage (d2-d5, d8).

During this period, the national branch of the Swiss social work professional organisation, AvenirSocial, was particularly active, issuing press releases to counter these political efforts and the accompanying negative media narratives. In one statement, AvenirSocial called for a more fact-based debate, arguing that to achieve cost savings, "we

Table 1. Overview of the Bern policy process and social workers' involvement in it

Strategy	Role	Agenda-Setting Phase	Policy Formulation Phase	Parliamentary Decision Phase	Direct-Democratic Decision Phase
Influencing policymakers	AvenirSocial leaders	X	X	X	
	BKSE leaders	X	X	X	
	Critical social workers		X		
	Members of parliament				
	Social services directors	X	X	X	
Organizing protest activities	Social services social workers			X	
	Verkeht activists			X	
	AvenirSocial leaders		X	X	X
	BKSE leaders				
	Critical social workers		X	X	
Mobilizing direct democracy	Members of parliament				
	Social services directors		X	X	
	Social services social workers		X	X	X
	Verkeht activists		X	X	X
	AvenirSocial leaders		X		X
Conducting media and public relations	BKSE leaders				
	Critical social workers		X		
	Members of parliament			X	
	Social services directors		X	X	X
	Social services social workers		X	X	X
Serving in parliament	Verkeht activists		X	X	X
	AvenirSocial leaders				
	BKSE leaders				
	Critical social workers				
	Members of parliament	X	X	X	X

need to combat poverty instead of punishing the poor” (d28). In this national context, and in response to a severe budget deficit (d92, d93, d104, d135, d268-271, sw22), the canton of Bern became one of the first cantons to place significant cuts to social assistance on its political agenda. In November 2012, a member of parliament from the right-wing Swiss People’s Party submitted a parliamentary motion proposing a 10% reduction in benefits relative to SKOS guidelines, projected to generate annual savings of CHF 22 million (d77, d272, d279).

Opposition to this proposal came from various social work actors, including members of parliament (sw21-23) who actively participated in the debates and the Bern Conference of Social Welfare and Child Protection (BKSE). BKSE is an association encompassing all 66 social services in the canton of Bern, with board members consisting of the directors of these services. The association’s mandate is to facilitate knowledge exchange, coordinate the implementation of social assistance within the canton, and advise the cantonal government on policy developments (d50, sw7-sw9). As part of its opposition, BKSE sent a letter to all members of parliament urging them to reject the proposed cuts (d40). AvenirSocial took a similar stance, emphasizing that further reductions in social assistance would “significantly impact the wellbeing of the most vulnerable members of society” (d131). These efforts to influence policymakers were bolstered by media and public relations initiatives. Leaders of AvenirSocial and BKSE, along with members of parliament, social services directors, and frontline social workers, expressed their positions through newspaper articles, interviews, and letters to the editor, publicly advocating against the cuts (e.g. d136-139).

As summarized in Table 1, social workers participated in the agenda-setting phase primarily as leaders of AvenirSocial and BKSE, social services directors, and members of parliament. Their objective was to prevent proposed cuts in social assistance from entering the political agenda by combining direct influence on policymakers with media and public

relations activities. Frontline social workers employed in social services, who voiced their expertise in letters to the editor, played only a minor role during this phase. Nevertheless, despite these interventions and in contrast to the cantonal government's position, the parliament approved the motion in September 2013, instructing the Ministry of Health and Social Affairs – led by a social democratic minister – to amend the Social Assistance Act and implement the proposed reduction (d105, d274).

Policy formulation

During the policy formulation phase, the Minister of Health and Social Affairs adopted a dual strategy. While preparing the legislative amendment, he simultaneously enacted incremental cost-cutting measures that did not require parliamentary approval (d48, d67-70, d77, sw22, sw29). From 2013 to 2016, these measures included freezing the basic subsistence allowance by suspending inflation adjustments and reducing the integration allowance to the minimum level recommended by SKOS (d48, d69, d140, d149). Additional changes targeted specific groups, such as young adults, and introduced stricter sanctions. By April 2016, the minister claimed that these cumulative measures had reduced annual costs by CHF 27 million, surpassing the CHF 22 million reduction demanded in the parliamentary motion (d77). This interpretation was later endorsed by BKSE leaders in a widely publicized press release, which provided a detailed calculation demonstrating how these incremental cuts collectively met the motion's cost-reduction target without the need for further measures (d48, d188).

Simultaneously, the ministry advanced legislative reform efforts. In April 2015, it published a first draft amendment aimed at formalizing previous cuts and introducing two additional measures: a cost ceiling for voluntary residential care placements and a further 15% reduction in benefits for young adults (d106-113). Leaders of AvenirSocial and BKSE, along with critical social workers and social services directors, responded to the draft with official

statements opposing further cuts (d15, d42, d59, sw1, sw3, sw6, sw14, sw17). Beyond these formal consultation responses, AvenirSocial leaders and critical social workers jointly launched a petition in 2014, gathering over 9,000 signatures to urge parliament to halt further reductions in social assistance (d25, sw6, sw22-sw23). Additionally, critical social workers organized a flash mob theatre performance to protest the cuts and raise public awareness (d58, sw27). The ministry's draft provoked strong opposition from social workers and polarized political reactions: left-leaning parties criticized the cuts as disproportionate, while right-leaning parties condemned them as insufficient.

Faced with the likelihood of parliamentary rejection, the Minister of Health and Social Affairs ultimately withdrew the draft and initiated a roundtable process aimed at achieving compromise (d114). In early 2016, three roundtable meetings brought together all major political parties. Sw23, who at the time was both a member of parliament and the BKSE director, participated in these discussions, albeit with limited success, as she belonged to the left-leaning minority. The process resulted in a second draft, which focused on reducing the entry-level benefit for new social assistance recipients (d74-d78). During the second consultation round, held in summer 2016, leaders of AvenirSocial and BKSE, along with critical social workers and social services directors, reiterated their position that the canton of Bern should continue to adhere to SKOS guidelines, unequivocally rejecting the revised draft (d16, d45, d62, sw30, sw33, sw37). This stance was supported by left-leaning parties, while right-leaning parties clearly called for deeper cuts (d114).

At this juncture, a profound political shift reshaped the reform process. The early resignation of the Social Democratic Minister of Health and Social Affairs prompted by elections in spring 2016, ending the left-leaning government's cohabitation with the conservative-right-dominated parliament. The right-wing Swiss People's Party seized the opportunity, gaining the Ministry of Health and Social Affairs – a position held by the Social

Democrats since 1976 (d10). The new right-wing minister took office in July 2016, placing the social assistance reform firmly under conservative leadership. Rejecting his predecessor's incremental approach, he pursued more far-reaching cuts. He drafted a third amendment proposing a uniform 10% reduction in the basic subsistence allowance for all recipients, combined with targeted cuts of 15-30% for young adults, temporarily admitted asylum seekers, and beneficiaries without basic proficiency in German or French. By framing earlier measures as insufficient to fulfill the parliamentary mandate (d80), the minister justified bypassing an additional consultation round and submitted the draft directly to parliament in June 2017 (d81, d114).

This decisive move elicited two main responses from social workers. First, leaders of AvenirSocial and BKSE, together with social services directors, sought to directly influence the minister. They organized meetings, submitted written briefs, extended invitations to visit service sites, and commissioned an impact study on the proposed cuts. These interventions had minimal observable effect on the minister's position. Second, in a collaborative effort between AvenirSocial, critical social workers, frontline social workers, and service users, the grassroots group Verkehrt was established. Financially supported by AvenirSocial, the group organized a large demonstration of over 800 participants in front of the cantonal parliament shortly after the minister's draft was published in June 2017 (d332, sw25).

As summarized in Table 1, social workers were involved in the policy formulation phase in all identified roles and strategies. While BKSE leaders and social services directors pursued insider influence through direct engagement with the Minister of Health and Social Affairs, critical social workers, Verkehrt activists, and frontline practitioners mobilized outside formal channels by organizing protest activities and initiating Verkehrt. AvenirSocial leaders were involved in both strategies. In collaboration with critical social workers, AvenirSocial also employed the petition as a direct-democratic instrument to express their

opposition to the proposed cuts. These approaches were complemented by media and public relations activities, including press releases and conferences, expert interviews, letters to the editor, social media efforts, and public information events.

Parliamentary decision

Between June and September 2017, the Parliamentary Committee of Health and Social Affairs, which included sw21 and sw23, reviewed the government's third draft and invited external experts to contribute to its discussions (d82, d115). During these hearings, BKSE leaders and social services directors shared their expertise (d275). For instance, sw9, then BKSE president, combined factual and emotional appeals by highlighting that one in ten children relies on social assistance and urging politicians to strengthen support rather than reduce benefits. Opponents contended that reductions would incentivize labor market integration and promote fairness between welfare recipients and taxpayers. Ultimately, the committee's majority endorsed the proposed cuts, recommending that parliament adopt the minister's draft (d82, d115).

The cantonal parliament debated the amendment in two plenary sessions held in December 2017 and March 2018. During these sessions, member of parliament sw22 warned of serious repercussions for vulnerable groups and opposed any further benefit reductions, while his more centrist colleague, sw21, proposed a 5% reduction as a compromise (d275-276). However, given the parliament's dominant conservative-right majority – 49 out of 160 seats were held by members of the right-wing Swiss People's Party alone – these positions had limited impact on the debate (d10).

Meanwhile, social workers operating outside parliament employed two main strategies to influence decision-making. First, leaders of AvenirSocial and BKSE, along with social services directors and frontline social workers, sought to shape parliamentary opinion through various lobbying efforts. AvenirSocial launched a systematic campaign, mobilizing and

training its members to approach parliamentarians (sw3, sw29, sw31). Similarly, BKSE leaders organized a lobbying event inside the parliamentary building (sw7, sw9, sw12) and invited members of parliament to visit social services offices to gain firsthand insight into the realities of social assistance (sw8, sw23). Additionally, the directors of five large social services proposed an alternative cost-saving plan that did not involve reducing the basic subsistence allowance (d120-126). However, this proposal was decisively rejected during the first plenary session (d275).

Second, alongside lobbying efforts, social workers participated in protest activities. During the parliamentary decision-making process, the Stop the Cut Collective emerged as a broad alliance of individuals and groups affected by the cuts. The group aimed to raise public awareness and pressure policymakers from outside parliament by organizing three demonstrations and two action days during the parliament's plenary sessions. AvenirSocial leaders, Verkehrt activists, critical social workers, frontline social workers, and service users joined these collective activities by posting on social media, distributing leaflets, and participating in the demonstrations (d294-320). Despite these efforts, the parliament adopted the amendment in March 2018, enacting an 8% reduction to the basic subsistence allowance for all recipients (d276).

As summarized in Table 1, social workers engaged in the parliamentary decision phase in three main ways. First, as members of parliament, they participated directly in committee and plenary deliberations. Second, led by AvenirSocial and BKSE leaders as well as social services directors, they engaged in diverse lobbying activities. Third, AvenirSocial leaders, critical social workers, frontline workers, and Verkehrt activists joined the Stop the Cut Collective's protest actions. While some of these efforts were supported by media and public relations strategies, only limited evidence of such approaches was found during this phase.

Direct-democratic decision

Anticipating parliamentary approval of the proposed cuts, opponents began preparing a referendum well in advance. By mid-2017, representatives from political parties, trade unions, members of parliament, social services directors, AvenirSocial leaders, Verkehrt activists, and service users formed a referendum committee. Their goal was to initiate a constructive referendum, a special type of referendum that not only rejects a new or amended law but proposes an alternative formulation instead (d1, d99). In this case, the referendum text – co-written by a social services director (d285) – called for increasing, rather than reducing, social assistance benefits (d283-290).

After the parliamentary approval of the amended Social Assistance Act in March 2018, the referendum committee had three months to collect the 10,000 signatures required to trigger a referendum. Between April and July 2018, under the leadership of the Social Democratic Party, the committee members mobilized extensively across the canton (sw20). AvenirSocial leaders and Verkehrt activists played particularly active roles, significantly contributing to the effort and helping to surpass the threshold with 16,321 validated signatures (d233, d280, d286, sw2, sw10, sw28, sw33). Frontline social workers also encouraged service users to sign the referendum (sw23).

In their responses to the referendum text, both parliament and government clearly opposed the alternative proposal in the fall of 2018 (d84-85, d117, d119, d277). To reinforce their stance, the right-wing Minister of Health and Social Affairs published cost estimates comparing the two competing proposals. He projected annual savings of CHF 18–31 million under the original plan but an increase of CHF 49–178 million under the alternative proposal (d84, d118). However, these figures were contested by the directors of three major social services, who issued their own calculations suggesting that the alternative proposal would increase costs by only CHF 3 million (d52, sw7). The ensuing controversy ahead of the vote

(d236-237) prompted parliament to commission an independent analysis (d278), which estimated annual savings of CHF 8–19 million for the original proposal and additional costs of CHF 17–28 million for the alternative proposal (d13). These neutral figures were subsequently included in the canton's official voter information brochure (d103).

In January 2019, the government scheduled the vote for May (d144). With the date confirmed, the involved actors officially launched their voting campaigns. The referendum committee coordinated a traditional, fact-oriented campaign that relied on posters, flyers, and press releases. Co-financed by AvenirSocial, this campaign emphasized the detrimental impact of the proposed cuts on children and older adults, aiming to inform and mobilize voters (d283-293, sw6). In parallel, but independently from the referendum committee, BKSE leaders undertook extensive media and public relations efforts. Their activities included publishing a position paper opposing the cuts (d53), producing an information booklet to explain the social assistance system to non-experts (d56, d245, sw7-8, sw14, sw29), engaging with the media through interviews and expert commentary (d263), and organizing events with social services directors and social workers to inform the public about the upcoming vote (sw10, sw17, sw29). Beyond BKSE leaders, media and public relations strategies were also employed by social workers in all other roles, except for critical social workers. For example, AvenirSocial leaders and members of parliament advocated their positions in public debates (sw6, sw23), social services directors and social workers encouraged service users to give interviews to newspapers (d252, sw24, sw31), and Verkehrt activists published a collection of statements opposing the cuts on social media (d350, sw32).

Complementing these formal approaches, Verkehrt activists initiated their own campaign, adopting a more creative and confrontational style. Funded by AvenirSocial, which provided CHF 50,000 (sw6, sw28-29), this campaign predominantly consisted of high-profile

protest activities in public spaces (d347, sw26, sw32-35). For example, they organized two flash mobs in one of Bern's central squares. The first, in March 2019, featured black posters predicting that the social assistance cuts would lead to "more illness, more despair, and more loneliness." The second flash mob, held shortly before the vote, replaced the black posters with yellow ones, promising that the alternative proposal would result in "more health, more perspectives, more togetherness" (d346, d348, sw32).

The policy process concluded on 19 May 2019, when voters rejected both the original and the alternative proposals (d100). Consequently, the existing Social Assistance Act remained in place. Nonetheless, the incremental reductions described earlier persisted, leaving social assistance at a lower baseline than in 2012. Since then, social assistance has remained a politically contentious issue in Bern and Switzerland, with social workers and social work organisations continuing to resist further retrenchment (d2, d5).

As summarized in Table 1, social workers engaged in the direct-democratic decision phase in three main ways. First, social workers in almost all roles were strongly involved in media and public relations strategies. Second, all examined social workers, except BKSE leaders and critical social workers, participated in mobilizing direct democracy. Third, with financial support from AvenirSocial, an extensive number of protest activities were organized by Verkehrt. Additionally, as in all phases of this policy process, social work members of parliament actively participated in the cantonal parliament, contributing to the debate on the constructive referendum and its associated costs.

Discussion

This study examined when, how, and in what roles social workers engaged in the policy process surrounding proposed reductions in social assistance in the Swiss canton of Bern between 2012 and 2019. The analysis reconstructed the process across four phases, identified seven distinct roles through which social workers participated, and mapped five main

strategies of policy engagement. By systematically linking strategies, timing, and roles, this study advances the literature on social workers' policy engagement, which has often treated these dimensions in isolation. Its main contribution lies in demonstrating how strategies were chosen, adapted, and combined across different roles and phases of the case, thereby offering a dynamic perspective on the interplay between context and action.

The Bern case unfolded across four main stages – agenda-setting, policy formulation, parliamentary decision, and direct-democratic decision – which broadly reflect the traditional stages in the policy cycle heuristic (Cairney, 2020). In contrast to much existing social work literature, which typically emphasizes agenda-setting, formulation, implementation, and evaluation (Benz & Rieger, 2015; De Corte & Roose, 2020; Klammer et al., 2019), this study highlights the analytical value of distinguishing the decision-making stage itself. Parliamentary deliberations emerged as a decisive arena of contestation in which social workers actively influenced policymakers. This finding resonates with earlier research on social workers' participation in parliamentary committees (Gal & Weiss-Gal, 2011; Weiss-Gal & Nouman, 2016) and suggests that future scholarship would benefit from closer attention to the decision stage. Such a focus can shed light on how social workers intervene in formal legislative processes and contribute to broader lobbying efforts (Rieger, 2024). Additionally, the direct-democratic decision phase proved crucial in the Swiss context. The referendum campaign constituted the culminating moment of the policy debate, during which social workers engaged heavily across multiple roles and strategies. Direct democracy thus added a distinct stage to the Bern case, highlighting how institutional context shapes the opportunities and arenas available for policy engagement. This dynamic vividly exemplifies Gal and Weiss-Gal's (2023a) Policy Engagement Conceptual Framework, which emphasizes, among other factors, the ways in which political opportunities influence the forms and levels of social workers' policy involvement. In this

regard, the constructive referendum can be understood as a specific instrument of direct democracy that created an additional pathway for social workers to intervene in the policy process (Kindler, 2024).

The analysis identified five main policy strategies, which cluster into insider and outsider categories (Cailleux, 2025; De Corte & Roose, 2020). Insider strategies included influencing policymakers and serving in parliament, while outsider strategies comprised organizing protest activities, mobilizing direct democracy, and conducting media and public relations. Among these, media and public relations were the most consistently used, appearing in all phases and across nearly all role types. This corresponds with previous research highlighting traditional and social media platforms as important tools for policy engagement (Dauti & Bejko, 2025; Manyama & Mvungi, 2017). In contrast, the other strategies followed a more phase-specific trajectory. In the early stages of the Bern case, social workers primarily focused on insider strategies, such as sending letters to policymakers, submitting consultation responses, and testifying before legislative committees. However, given the strong conservative-right majority in both parliament and government, these efforts proved largely ineffective. Consequently, social workers increasingly shifted to outsider strategies, including petitions, flash mobs, and demonstrations. The two approaches overlapped during the formulation and parliamentary decision phases, but following parliamentary approval of the cuts, engagement moved almost entirely to outsider strategies, culminating in the referendum campaign. Taken together, the analysis demonstrates how social workers adapted their strategies across the policy process: initially seeking to influence policymakers, then organizing protest activities, and ultimately mobilizing direct democracy. This trajectory illustrates how changing structural conditions, such as parliamentary majorities and the availability of direct-democratic instruments, shaped the strategic repertoire of social workers (Gal & Weiss-Gal, 2023a). Finally, whereas earlier research has shown that social workers

tend to prefer collaborative and consensus-oriented approaches (Dauti & Bejko, 2024; Gal & Weiss-Gal, 2023b; Gilboa & Weiss-Gal, 2022; Guidi et al., 2025), the present findings demonstrate their capacity to adopt confrontational strategies, thereby adding nuance to understandings of their engagement in policy processes.

The findings further demonstrate that strategies were closely tied to social workers' roles. In line with their more formal positions within parliament or administration, social work members of parliament, BKSE leaders, and social services directors primarily relied on insider strategies such as lobbying and legislative work. By contrast, Verkehrt activists, critical social workers, and frontline practitioners were more strongly, or even exclusively, engaged in outsider strategies, including protests and referendum mobilization. AvenirSocial leaders were distinctive in that they consistently combined insider and outsider approaches, engaging in lobbying and direct-democratic mobilization while simultaneously supporting the organization of protest activities. These results resonate with recent political science scholarship that challenges the insider-outsider dichotomy. From this perspective, AvenirSocial and its leaders can be considered "unnatural insiders" (O'Brien et al., 2023), as they are traditionally outside actors yet possess the resources, expertise, and networks to employ both insider and outsider strategies (Cailleux, 2025). However, AvenirSocial leaders were not the only ones to adopt combined approaches. Social workers across nearly all roles employed media and public relations in conjunction with other strategies. For example, social work members of parliament reinforced their parliamentary work with newspaper statements or public debates; BKSE leaders combined parliamentary lobbying with public information events; and Verkehrt activists deliberately used protest actions to attract media attention. Taken together, these findings suggest that social workers' policy engagement is best understood as a dynamic interplay between their roles and the use of multiple, often complementary, strategies.

Finally, the findings highlight the pivotal role of AvenirSocial, the Swiss social work professional organization. Gal and Weiss-Gal (2023a) emphasize that professional organizations can act both as proxies and as recruitment networks. In the Bern case, AvenirSocial leaders fulfilled both functions: they represented their members, and social workers more broadly, by influencing policymakers and conducting media and public relations. In this way, individual social workers who were reluctant to engage directly in policy or who feared repercussions from their employers were nevertheless represented in the policy process through their professional organization. At the same time, AvenirSocial served as a recruitment network by mobilizing social workers to contact politicians or to join the Verkehrt group, thereby broadening collective resistance to the planned cuts (Moth et al., 2024). Beyond these established roles, AvenirSocial leaders also played a decisive part in establishing and financing Verkehrt, effectively outsourcing a substantial share of policy engagement. Financial sponsorship, therefore, could be considered a third subtype of policy involvement by professional organizations, complementing the roles of proxy and recruitment network. These findings confirm the central policy role of professional organizations identified in prior scholarship (Guidi, 2020, 2025) and point to the need for future research to examine not only the policy engagement of individual social workers but also of collective actors, such as professional organizations, employers, or trade unions.

In addition to this individualistic focus, several limitations of this research should be acknowledged. First, while the analysis offers a rich account of social workers' engagement across multiple phases of a policy process, its grounding in Switzerland's distinctive direct-democratic framework restricts the transferability of the findings to other political and cultural contexts. Nonetheless, given that welfare retrenchment and neoliberal reforms are unfolding in many settings, it remains highly relevant to investigate whether similar patterns of engagement emerge elsewhere. Future research should therefore build on both comparable

and contrasting cases, ideally within comparative designs, to further illuminate how social workers engage in resisting adverse policy developments. Furthermore, this focus on social workers' opposition to a detrimental policy reform should be complemented by studies that investigate instances in which social workers act as policy initiators. Such analyses would make it possible to explore whether these different forms of engagement correspond to distinct strategies, roles, and timing in the policy process. Finally, many participants in this study simultaneously occupied multiple roles. While the present analysis examined these roles separately, such compartmentalization risks overlooking how role accumulation shapes the dynamics of policy engagement. Future research should therefore investigate how overlapping roles interact to amplify or constrain social workers' involvement in policy processes.

Conclusion

This study examined how social workers engaged in the policy process surrounding planned cuts to social assistance in the Swiss canton of Bern. By tracing the agenda-setting, policy formulation, parliamentary decision, and direct-democratic decision phases, the analysis identified seven roles and five strategies through which social workers participated. The findings reveal that social workers were active across multiple phases and roles, ranging from institutional actors such as parliamentarians, social services directors, and professional association leaders to critical social workers, grassroots activists, and frontline practitioners. Strategies evolved over time in response to changing political circumstances. Early insider approaches, such as lobbying and consultation, transitioned to outsider tactics, including protest activities and referendum mobilization, when parliamentary majorities limited the effectiveness of direct influence. Media and public relations emerged as a consistent cross-cutting strategy used across phases and roles, often in combination with other strategies. These findings nuance earlier claims that social workers predominantly prefer consensus-

oriented approaches by demonstrating their capacity to adopt confrontational and contentious strategies when political circumstances warrant. Additionally, the findings highlight how specific roles influenced the choice of strategies: formal positions facilitated insider influence, while more informal, activist roles were associated with outsider strategies. Together, this case study provides an in-depth account of social workers' involvement in policy, emphasizing how their engagement is shaped by the dynamic interplay of roles, strategies, and political timing.

Ethics statement

The study was approved by the Ethics Committee of the Paul Baerwald School of Social Work and Social Welfare at the Hebrew University of Jerusalem [confirmation number 09102022]. All participants provided written informed consent prior to participating.

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CHAPTER 4

Social work and policy engagement: A thematic analysis of Swiss social workers' policy strategies

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Social work and policy engagement: A thematic analysis of Swiss social workers' policy strategies

Abstract

An expanding body of theoretical literature reconceptualises social work not merely as a mechanism for policy implementation but as an active policy actor. From this perspective, social workers are encouraged to leverage their professional expertise to shape policy development in ways that promote equity, justice, and the overall wellbeing of service users. Despite this evolving discourse, empirical research on policy engagement remains scarce, providing only limited knowledge about social workers' particular policy strategies. Addressing this research gap, the aim of this qualitative case study was to gain a deeper understanding of how social workers engage in policy processes. More precisely, it drew on interviews with 38 social workers to examine their strategies of policy engagement in the real policy case of planned cuts to public social assistance in the canton of Bern in Switzerland. The data were analysed using thematic analysis, which yielded seven distinct policy strategies: influencing formal policymaking, shaping public opinion, building coalitions, mobilising engagement, creating emotional involvement, contributing professional knowledge, and involving service users. These findings reinforce existing frameworks, highlight previously underexplored policy strategies, and suggest promising directions for future empirical research on social workers' policy engagement.

Introduction

Social work and the making of social policy have always been closely intertwined (Burzlaff, 2022; Klammer et al., 2019; Rieger, 2021). Beyond simply implementing policy, social workers leverage their professional expertise to inform decision-making and advocate for more just policies. This dimension of practice, referred to as policy engagement, denotes the intentional activities through which practitioners seek to influence the development, implementation, or evaluation of public policies (Gal & Weiss-Gal, 2023a; Jansson, 2018).¹ As a distinct facet of professional practice, policy engagement features prominently in both national and international ethical guidelines (e.g. AvenirSocial, 2010; NASW, 2021). For example, the International Association of Schools of Social Work (IASSW) and the International Federation of Social Workers (IFSW) state in their commentary notes for the global definition that “social work practice spans a range of activities including (...) policy formulation and analysis; and advocacy and political interventions” (IASSW & IFSW, 2014).

Herz and Bečević (2024) argue that in order to live up to these “high-held ambitions of the profession (...), social workers need to approach the world politically” (p. 13). Such a political approach to the world has been increasingly discussed in conceptual and theoretical contributions, with an emphasis on “thinking social work politically” (Bečević & Herz, 2023) and conceptualising social workers as policy actors (e.g. De Corte & Roose, 2020; Marston & McDonald, 2012). Concurrently with these conceptual advances, empirical research on social workers’ policy engagement has grown substantially, with quantitative studies predominating (Gal & Weiss-Gal, 2023b; Weiss-Gal, 2017). Previous studies examined the extent of policy engagement (e.g. Burzlaff et al., 2025; Carvalho et al., 2025; Guidi et al., 2025) and identified

¹ Given this study’s focus on social workers’ policy engagement, it is essential to distinguish ‘policy engagement’ from the broader construct of ‘political engagement’, which comprises variables such as political interest, political efficacy, political knowledge, and party identification that affect the level and forms of policy involvement (Schlozman et al., 2018).

motivational, organisational, institutional, and environmental predictors of such engagement (e.g. Demircali et al., 2024; Nouman, 2025; Schwartz-Tayri, 2021; Weiss-Gal & Gal, 2020). Additional research has focused on the specific strategies and techniques that social workers employ to influence policy outcomes, from lobbying and coalition-building to grassroots protests (e.g. Dauti & Bejko, 2024, 2025; Gal & Weiss-Gal, 2025).

While these studies provide valuable insights, their predominantly quantitative approaches tend to produce abstract, aggregated findings that may overlook the concrete ways in which social workers engage in policymaking. Qualitative research on real-life policy cases, which could capture social workers' strategies of policy engagement in more nuanced ways, remains scarce (e.g. Aviv et al., 2021; Rieger & Wurtzbacher, 2020; Tzadiki & Weiss-Gal, 2021). To address this gap, the present case study aimed to gain a deeper understanding of how social workers engage in policy. More precisely, it drew on interviews with social workers to examine their strategies of policy engagement in the specific policy case of planned cuts to public social assistance (PSA) in the canton of Bern in Switzerland.

Policy context: the case of proposed reductions to PSA in the canton of Bern

The policy strategies of Swiss social workers are framed by Switzerland's consensus-oriented combination of direct democracy and federalism. Direct democratic instruments – initiatives and referendums – operate at federal, cantonal and local levels, providing policy actors, including social workers, with opportunities to influence policy both within and outside parliamentary processes (Linder & Mueller, 2021). Federalism further decentralises power by delegating substantial autonomy to the 26 cantons, which play a central role in developing and implementing social policy measures (Ladner, 2019). An illustrative case of cantonal sovereignty is the regulation of PSA, Switzerland's last-resort safety net for people in poverty covering housing, health, and basic living costs. As one of the largest employment sectors for social workers, PSA varies considerably across cantons, reflecting the federalist

structure and divergent cantonal priorities. To mitigate this fragmentation, the Swiss Conference on Social Welfare (SKOS) issues non-binding guidelines aimed at harmonising PSA implementation nationwide (Kindler, 2024; Madörin et al., 2017).

Despite these coordination efforts, the early 2000s saw mounting criticism of PSA from conservative factions. The canton of Bern emerged as a pioneer in this debate when a Swiss People's Party MP lodged a parliamentary motion in 2012 seeking a ten-percent reduction in PSA benefits relative to SKOS recommendations (Keller, 2025; Parliament Canton Bern, 2012). The cantonal parliament endorsed the motion in 2013, mandating the government to draft the requisite legal amendments (State Chancellery Canton Bern, 2013). Subsequent draft proposals in 2015 and 2016 were heavily criticised by experts and party leaders: the left found the cuts too drastic, while the right deemed them insufficient (Government Canton Bern, 2015, 2017). In 2017, a third revised draft amendment proposing a ten percent reduction in PSA benefits for all service users was published and sent to the cantonal parliament (Government Canton Bern, 2017). During parliamentary debates in 2017 and 2018, the majority of MPs agreed that a ten-percent cut was too severe, with some advocating for a five percent reduction. Ultimately, a compromise was reached, and the amendment was passed with an eight percent reduction for all service users (State Chancellery Canton Bern, 2017, 2018).

Alongside the formal policy formulation process in parliament, social work actors opposed the planned PSA cuts from outside of the parliament: One of the main driving forces behind this effort was a coalition called 'Verkehrt', which brought together critical social workers, the Swiss social work professional organisation (AvenirSocial), frontline social workers, students, and service users. The title 'Verkehrt', meaning 'the wrong way', expressed the coalition's belief that cutting PSA was fundamentally wrong (Verkehrt, 2018). In addition to Verkehrt, the Bern Conference of Social Welfare and Child Protection (BKSE) – a professional association uniting all 66 social services in the canton – strongly opposed the cuts.

The activity of these social work actors peaked when parliament decided to reduce PSA benefits in 2018. Led by the Social Democratic Party, representatives from other political parties, social services, trade unions, AvenirSocial, Verkehrt, MPs, and service users initiated a constructive referendum. This direct democratic tool not only overrides parliamentary decisions but proposes alternative policies instead (Glaser et al., 2016). In this case, instead of cutting benefits, the referendum committee proposed to increase them, especially for people over 55. Between April and July 2018, the committee collected more than 16,000 signatures, exceeding the threshold of 10,000 signatures required to trigger a referendum. The referendum was held on three options: the parliamentary proposal, the alternative proposed by the referendum committee, or a rejection of both (Government Canton Bern, 2018).

Once enough signatures had been gathered and it became clear that a referendum vote was imminent, the actors shifted their mode of engagement. Between fall 2018 and spring 2019, their goal was to inform the public and mobilise citizens to vote against PSA cuts (Moth et al., 2024; Verkehrt, 2018). In the May 2019 vote, both the parliament's and the referendum committee's proposals were rejected, ultimately discarding the radical cuts originally proposed in 2012 (State Chancellery Canton Bern, 2019). This multi-faceted cantonal process, encompassing both parliamentary and extra-parliamentary arenas, offers a useful empirical basis for examining social workers' policy activities in a real-world context. Accordingly, the study was designed to address the following research question: What strategies of policy engagement did social workers employ in response to the planned cuts to PSA in the canton of Bern between 2012 and 2019?

Methods

Sampling and data generation

The study is based on problem-centred interviews (Witzel & Reiter, 2012). Participants were selected using snowball and purposive sampling techniques. They were included in the

study if they were involved in the policy process described above, were employed as a social worker at the time, and had a degree that formally qualified them as a social worker. These criteria ensured that respondents could meaningfully inform the research question, albeit with a bias toward more visibly engaged practitioners. The interviews were conducted between June and November 2023. They lasted between 29 and 107 min ($M = 75$, $SD = 17$) and were conducted in a location of the interviewee's choice. The thematic interview guide began with questions about the general context of the policy case and respondents' policy engagement. This was followed by specific prompts to explore how participants were involved in the policy process, including examples of their strategies. All interviews were conducted in Swiss German, audio-taped and transcribed into German. The transcripts were then slightly edited for readability and translated for this article. Participants are referred to using unique numerical pseudonyms (sw1–sw38) to ensure their anonymity. The study was approved by the Ethics Committee of the Paul Baerwald School of Social Work and Social Welfare at the Hebrew University of Jerusalem [09102022] and all interviewees gave written informed consent.

Participants

A total of 38 social workers were interviewed. Respondents self-identified as female ($n = 16$) and male ($n = 22$). Their mean age was 48 years ($SD = 12$) with a range of 31 to 67 years. They averaged 20 years ($SD = 11$, range: 5-44) of social work experience. All respondents had a bachelor's ($n = 23$) or master's degree in social work ($n = 15$). Participants were involved in the policy case in a variety of roles, including positions in several organisations introduced in the previous section. The largest groups comprised directors ($n = 13$) and frontline social workers in social services ($n = 11$). Nine participants held leadership roles in BKSE (president, board member, director), and six served as AvenirSocial leaders (including the national association's director and cantonal board members). In addition, interviewees were active in social movements: five were critical social workers, and 18

participated as activists in the Verkehrt coalition described above. Furthermore, four participants were members of the cantonal parliament. Most of the interviewees were involved in multiple roles. For example, sw29 was a Verkehrt activist, a social services director, and a BKSE leader at the same time. More details on the socio-demographic and professional background of the participants can be found in the supplemental online material.

Data analysis

The data were analysed using thematic analysis as introduced by Braun and Clarke (2022). First, all transcripts were re-read in detail to deepen the understanding of their content. Second, the entire data set was coded, and all codes and relevant data extracts were collated. Third, through close examination of these codes, initial themes were constructed. Fourth, the codes and initial themes were reviewed against the coded data extracts and the entire dataset to determine if they fit the data well and address the research question. In this way, both codes and themes were further developed. The fifth phase consisted of finalising theme development. This included refining, defining, and naming the themes. Both coding and theme development followed an iterative, inductive approach until a coherent set of named themes was reached, providing a rich and detailed picture of social workers' strategies of policy engagement. Thematic analysis was supported by qualitative data analysis software, MAXQDA 24. The analysis was conducted by the author and critically discussed in research seminars, scientific conferences, and regular meetings with peer researchers.

Findings

The following seven themes were developed in the analysis, representing distinct strategies of social workers' policy engagement: Influencing formal policymaking, shaping public opinion, building coalitions, mobilising engagement, creating emotional involvement, contributing professional knowledge, and involving service users. The following sections elaborate on each of these strategies.

Influencing formal policymaking

While the original idea of reducing PSA was presented in 2012, it was not until 2018 that the parliament finally decided to cut financial benefits by eight percent. Throughout this period, social workers sought to influence formal political decision-making through direct interaction with politicians, by holding elected office as MPs, and by using direct democratic tools. It was primarily representatives of more formal social work groups – i.e., AvenirSocial and BKSE – who directly interacted with politicians. In their efforts to prevent further cutbacks during the parliamentary debate, they approached MPs personally in both formal and informal settings, organised lobbying events in parliament, and invited politicians to visit social services to learn first-hand how the proposed cuts could be counterproductive for both service users and broader social welfare goals. Social workers made particular efforts to convince members of conservative parties to vote against the proposal, as they held a majority in parliament at the time. However, as illustrated in the following statement by sw14, a social services director, most of these efforts were ultimately perceived as unsuccessful:

“I was in personal contact with two MPs from my region and tried to show them what was happening here – without success. One of them is indeed on the far right. The other also represents the conservative Swiss People’s Party, but I had hoped to win him over because he had long served as president of the social committee and was even, for a time, involved as a board member of the local social services. He actually knows what it’s all about. However, during this cantonal political process, party ideology ultimately overshadowed everything.”

Four of the social workers interviewed were themselves members of the cantonal parliament during this period and were thus involved in one of the most direct forms of policy engagement. They belonged to the Green, Green Liberal, Left and Social Democratic parties and used their formal positions to influence policy from within. When asked about her

motivation for holding office and how this differed from extra-parliamentary policy strategies, sw24 argued that “the parliament is just a tool. It’s simply where decisions are, de facto, ultimately made.” Other social workers did not hold office but used their membership in mostly left-of-centre political parties to advise and consult their representatives.

Outside parliament, social workers used direct democratic tools to influence the formal policymaking process. AvenirSocial, BKSE, Verkehrt, directors of social services and critical social workers submitted statements, position papers and a petition to lobby against the cuts or were actively involved in collecting signatures for the referendum after the final decision of the parliament to reduce PSA.

Shaping public opinion

In addition to influencing formal political decision-making, the social workers interviewed employed a wide range of visual campaigning, protest activities, and media outreach to shape public opinion against the proposed cuts. One of the main driving forces behind these efforts was the extra-parliamentary Verkehrt group. They launched a two-part visual campaign, initially featuring stark black posters with slogans such as “You want more illness? Cut social assistance”, then switching to bright yellow messages like “You want more health? Don’t cut social assistance!” Verkehrt members used these materials on the streets, distributing leaflets, stickers, soup packets, and even bike-saddle covers, while often engaging passersby in conversations about the upcoming vote. They also showcased these visuals at large, colourful demonstrations, flashmobs, and other public protests, sometimes joined by entire social services teams from across the canton. Reflecting on the first major demonstration in 2016, sw28, one of the organisers, recalled:

“I was absolutely blown away by how many people showed up at the demonstration. I also think it was definitely worth creating the printed materials – demonstration materials that were printed on large posters. You could see them in the newspapers

everywhere the next day. And I believe that this graphic, symbolic approach had a real public impact that shouldn't be underestimated."

Both the visual campaign and protest activities were reinforced by consistent (social) media work aimed at further shaping public opinion. Some tactics were chosen primarily because they were likely to attract press coverage, as sw6, one of the AvenirSocial leaders, explained:

"The point of a flashmob is to get eye-catching photos and give the media a story. It worked well and the newspaper ran a full-page article about the flashmob and our cause. It was a complete success."

In addition to these activist strategies used by Verkehrt, more formal social work actors also used the media to speak out against the welfare cuts. For instance, directors of social services appeared in newspaper and television interviews, and the BKSE issued press releases strongly opposing the cuts. Other means of shaping public opinion included submitting letters to the editor, publishing online comments, arranging for service users to be interviewed, participating in panel discussions, or gathering celebrity endorsements against the cuts and sharing them online.

Building coalitions

Another key strategy of social workers' policy engagement was coalition building. Many of the interviewed social workers emphasised how important it was to join forces, both formally and informally, with other groups and associations in order to oppose the cuts. sw3, one of the AvenirSocial leaders, recalled how the Verkehrt coalition emerged:

"It all went a bit uncoordinated at first, at least that's how I felt. And then we tried to mobilise everyone who could do something in this area. (...) As a first step, we organised a meeting – inviting members of AvenirSocial, but also of other groups, particularly of the critical social work forum, which was very active back then. And we

tried to bring everyone together a bit. I think that wasn't so easy, because the critical social workers couldn't necessarily fully identify with AvenirSocial. And yes, that was the goal: to truly bring everyone together in order to pursue a common objective."

Creating a sense of belonging and a shared vision within sometimes heterogeneous groups was also mentioned by other interviewees as an important element of coalition building. sw20 shared that she was excited to experience what she called "a community of social workers", and sw1 felt that – despite sometimes differing political attitudes – the almost unanimous opposition to the planned cuts was a "common denominator" among all social workers in the canton and beyond. While united by a common cause, the coalition partners contributed to it in different ways. The emerging coalitions strategically used their diverse backgrounds to complement one another's approaches and effectively engage different audiences, as sw7, one of the BKSE leaders, explained:

"We always considered who would take on which role – what hats we could wear and who should wear which hat. We then tried to distribute these hats. This is a strategy that social work, with its already established network, can use very successfully if done well – ensuring that not everyone wears the same hat, so that different groups and people can be reached."

To coordinate the different approaches of the many actors involved, several interviewees assumed the role of pontifices – building bridges, transporting information or exchanging ideas among different coalition partners and allies. Leveraging their extensive networks, it was primarily MPs, the director of AvenirSocial or directors of major social services who actively participated in multiple groups simultaneously, helping to build and maintain coalitions. The interviewed social workers highlighted resource sharing as a key advantage of coalition partnerships. sw29, a central figure in establishing Verkehrt, described AvenirSocial's significant financial support as a "game changer" for its development, adding

that “alliances ultimately lead to money, structures and resources.” In addition to financial contributions, coalition partners shared their personal networks, position papers and other materials – such as brochures detailing facts and figures about the planned PSA reduction – to create synergies and advance their common goals.

Mobilising engagement

In parallel with coalition building, the strategy of mobilising engagement aimed to further strengthen the joint efforts against the cuts. This approach focused on engaging people in concrete actions – such as participating in demonstrations and voting – while also inviting them to join and actively contribute to emerging groups and coalitions on a more permanent basis. Notably, this strategy of policy engagement was mentioned almost exclusively by Verkehrt members, whereas representatives from more established organisations like BKSE did not report any specific mobilisation activities. Verkehrt members leveraged both personal and professional networks to mobilise people for concrete action. They invited colleagues, friends, and family to engage in protest activities and voting, with a particular emphasis on motivating those who typically abstain in order to increase voter turnout. This strategy was exemplified by sw25’s account, in which she stated:

“And then we realized, okay, within our circles – and beyond that – there are simply a lot of people in Switzerland, when you look at voter turnout, who don’t vote. And then we discovered that we should focus on them. (...) We decided that they are our target group.”

In addition to mobilising people for one-off activities, Verkehrt also focused on recruiting individuals for longer-term engagement. Even when the coalition was more established, the group maintained an inclusive approach that welcomed new members. As sw32 noted, “we simply said, yes, everyone should come – it’s open to all.” Verkehrt organised so-called “Bazars” that were intended to offer easy-accessible opportunities for

participation. sw30, one of the organisers, described these meetings as follows:

“Our idea was that by hosting these bazar meetings in Bern and in various surrounding regions, (...) we could engage with other social workers who would become actively involved and help disseminate the information – whether through their social services, workplaces, or even directly on the streets.”

To complement these networking and bazar approaches, Verkehrt used online communication channels to mobilise supporters beyond their own personal and professional circles. They regularly promoted upcoming meetings and activities on social media and their website, circulated newsletters, and actively invited the wider community to get involved. sw33 and sw34, two Verkehrt activists, meticulously examined the websites of all local social service organisations in the canton to compile a comprehensive list of the work email addresses of their social workers. They then used this list to update their colleagues on Verkehrt’s goals, activities, and initiatives, inspiring them to take action.

Creating emotional involvement

“If you want to achieve political success, you have to work with emotions,” said sw9, one of the BKSE leaders. And indeed, creating emotional involvement emerged as a recurring strategy of social workers’ policy engagement. This approach was employed to influence both formal policymaking and public opinion by appealing to people’s empathy, solidarity and sense of injustice. Recounting his lobbying efforts with MPs, sw9 further explained:

“These people are too detached – they have no idea. And sure, I’m being manipulative. I try to engage them on an emotional level because numbers and facts just don’t work. You have to implant vivid images in these politicians’ minds. (...) And that was the whole point: to present certain statistics or, as I said, to set images in their minds. For example, that one in ten children in wealthy Switzerland lives on social assistance. Just imagine that.”

In addition to creating emotional involvement among formal decision makers, social workers also employed this strategy to shape public opinion, an approach used mainly by Verkehrt. Its public campaign was strategically designed to evoke a range of emotional reactions, including anger, irritation, shock, laughter or lingering questions. For example, sw31 noted that during one of the flashmobs, a speaker ironically advocated for PSA cuts alongside increased loneliness, illness, and child poverty, aiming to “showcase the symptoms” of radical welfare reduction. sw28 described such approaches as having a legitimate “populist drive”, and sw26 further specified that it was precisely this “unconventional” and “provocative language” that resonated particularly well with young people.

Like Verkehrt, social workers in more formal positions also recognised the power of emotions to shape public opinion, particularly through media channels. For example, sw8, BKSE leader and social services director, recalled that journalists “were very appreciative of bold statements”, adding that in one of the interviews he “absolutely came across as a provocateur, which really caused a lot of anger from one of the members of the government”. Reflecting on his strategic use of emotions, sw8 emphasised the importance of distinguishing between roles: as the director of social services, he felt free to express emotional statements in support of his municipality and his organisation, whereas his role as BKSE leader required a strictly “fact-based” approach – an important aspect of the theme presented in the next section.

Contributing professional knowledge

Social workers also contributed their professional knowledge to influence formal policymaking and shape public opinion. This strategy primarily utilised three channels: organising information events, disseminating information materials and raising awareness face-to-face. A wide range of formal and informal social work groups organised local and regional public information events, sometimes in close cooperation with other actors, such as churches, municipalities, or NGOs. According to sw29, the aim of these events was “to

present the idea behind the planned cuts, give information on the current situation and describe the changes to be expected at various levels.” To achieve these objectives, social workers provided real case studies or actively involved the audience in calculating sample welfare budgets to illustrate the impact of further cuts. sw17, a social services director, captured this approach when he stated:

“During this event we created a budget together with the people in the room to determine the financial needs of a family with two children. We asked everyone to provide their estimates, then immediately updated those numbers in Excel, which produced a specific total. We then said, alright, you believe that with this amount of money you’ll get by as a family, it shouldn’t be less. However, when we compared the calculated total with the actual welfare benefits, it was clearly insufficient. This comparison sparked a real lightbulb moment.”

Alongside these events, social workers developed materials to provide the public with essential background information, facts, and figures about the PSA system. One of the most influential of these publications was a booklet released by BKSE several months before the vote. sw7, BKSE leader and the driving force behind the booklet, explained:

“We invested a few thousand francs. We wanted a printed product that could be handed out at various events. (...) We were also able to give it to all the partners and churches that organised their own events. That way, we didn’t have to be on-site everywhere, but were represented through the booklets. The language was very clear, very simple, and in no way politically inflammatory. There was no political message in it (...), but it simply stated that the current system was good.”

In these efforts to influence politicians and the public, social workers also drew on empirical evidence and statistical data as part of their professional knowledge. Using published results from recent studies, they warned of the negative effects of further cuts in

PSA and highlighted that two thirds of welfare recipients were either children or part of the working poor. This academic knowledge was complemented by insights gained from social workers' day-to-day experience, which added to their credibility in face-to-face advocacy against the cuts. For instance, sw23 was highly recognised by her parliamentary colleagues for her expertise, as she was the only MP at the time with firsthand professional experience in PSA.

Involving service users

As most interviewees worked directly with PSA recipients on a daily basis, another key policy strategy specifically targeted this group. Many participants considered it their professional duty to inform service users about the planned cuts and to mobilise them to resist, an approach also echoed by sw37, a frontline social worker, who noted:

“Our task is not only to facilitate labour market and health integration, but also social integration. And engaging with political issues is part of social integration. From my perspective, social work is always about empowering individuals. Empowering them so that they can participate in political processes or at least know what they are about especially now, when there is an issue that has a direct impact on their daily lives.”

The social workers involved used face-to-face counselling sessions and distributed written materials – sometimes adapted for people with limited reading skills – to raise awareness among service users. They informed them about democratic rights, gave details of upcoming demonstrations, and provided concrete calculations illustrating how the proposed cuts would reduce monthly benefits. Beyond sharing information, many actively encouraged service users to advocate for themselves and take part in the policy process, whether through voting or demonstrating. In some cases, they even offered material support, such as covering the cost of train tickets to demonstrations or postage stamps to vote by mail, using funds from their agencies.

In addition to informing and mobilising service users, some social workers also collaborated with them to oppose the proposed cuts. A particularly strong collaboration between professionals and service users emerged in the Verkehrt group, where service users helped shape the campaign using their perspective and “very concrete examples from their everyday life as a person directly affected by poverty” (sw26).

While they emphasised the importance of involving service users, the interview partners also warned of a fine line between such efforts and instrumentalisation. Some worried that issuing explicit voting recommendations would compromise professional boundaries and risk veering into manipulation. Others noted the delicate position of public servants, who had to avoid accusations of political interference. Nonetheless, most interviewees felt that it was legitimate – and even necessary – to highlight the significance of the referendum, especially for vulnerable individuals who were sometimes unaware of how it could impact their everyday life. This perspective was succinctly illustrated by sw14, a social services director, when he stated:

“In response to the referendum vote that was taking place we organised a small initiative to make our clients aware of their right to vote and encouraged them to exercise it. However, we did not give any voting recommendations or anything like that. Our goal was simply to motivate them by saying: This is an issue that affects you. Engage with it. And if it matters to you, go and vote.”

Discussion

This study set out to gain a deeper understanding of how social workers engage in policymaking. To do so, it examined the broad diversity of social workers’ policy strategies in response to the planned PSA cuts in the canton of Bern in Switzerland between 2012 and 2019. The findings demonstrate that the interviewees not only thought about social work politically (Bečević & Herz, 2023) but also actively assumed the role of policy actors. To

explore their specific actions to counteract these reductions in more detail, an inductive thematic analysis developed the following seven strategies of social workers' policy engagement: Influencing formal policymaking, shaping public opinion, building coalitions, mobilising engagement, creating emotional involvement, contributing professional knowledge, and involving service users.

Established theoretical frameworks are useful to further characterise these strategies. Drawing on Jansson's (2018) policy practice framework, social workers in the Bern case can be clearly defined as policy opposers rather than policy initiators, bystanders, or responders, as all their strategies were aimed at preventing the proposed cuts. In addition, Rieger (2021) suggested distinguishing between social workers' internal (policy implementation) and external (policy formulation) forms of engagement, and their direct (advocacy on behalf of service users) and indirect (empowerment and self-advocacy of service users) types of involvement. Through the lens of this typology, the policy strategies of social workers in this case are predominantly external and direct. However, certain strategies – most notably “involving service users” – also integrate indirect elements of policy engagement. A third useful model to better understand social workers' involvement in the Bern case is the policy engagement framework and its six routes of policy engagement, introduced by Gal and Weiss-Gal (2023a). The social workers interviewed were involved in four of these six routes, namely in voluntary political participation, holding elected office, policy practice, and through the policy involvement of professional organisations, such as AvenirSocial and BKSE. While these frameworks are valuable for capturing the broader aspects of social workers' policy engagement, they remain inherently abstract in nature. The analysis in this study adds to these conceptualisations by providing a more fine-grained account of specific policy strategies, along with examples of how opposing (Jansson, 2018), external, direct, and indirect policy engagement (Rieger, 2021) looks like in practice.

In contrast to previous qualitative studies that focused on distinct types of policy engagement – such as policy entrepreneurship (Aviv et al., 2021; Cohen, 2021), policy practice (Dauti & Bejko, 2024, 2025; Gal & Weiss-Gal, 2025), or holding political office (Kindler & Amann, 2022; Löffler, 2024) – this study used a real case to explore the rich diversity of social workers’ policy strategies. On the one hand, this approach identified similar policy strategies to those found in previous research. For instance, influencing formal policymaking, shaping public opinion, coalition building, mobilising engagement, and leveraging professional knowledge to influence policy were central results in earlier research and are now reinforced by the findings of this study. On the other hand, the present analysis uncovered two important, yet previously underexplored, strategies that further expand the discourse on social workers’ policy engagement. First, emotions, although increasingly discussed as an important part of social work practice (e.g. Ingram, 2015; O’Connor, 2022; Sicora, 2022) or described as “fuel for political action” (Bečević & Herz, 2023), have not been identified as core aspects of social workers’ policy strategies in earlier research. Similarly, the involvement of service users does not feature prominently in most of the current policy engagement frameworks, with only Rieger (2021) who describes empowerment and self-advocacy of service users as indirect policy intervention. Reflecting this marginalisation, the present study is one of the first to examine service user involvement as a distinct policy strategy of social workers. Although mobilising and educating service users are important facets of participatory policy engagement explicitly mentioned in professional codes of ethics (e.g. AvenirSocial, 2010; NASW, 2021), such efforts frequently raise complex ethical dilemmas. Practitioners may find themselves torn between allegiance to service users’ interests and the priorities of their employing agencies or policymakers, and between upholding self-determination and avoiding paternalistic overreach. Recent conceptual advances, such as the policy practice ethical dilemmas framework (Weiss-Gal et al., 2024),

address these dilemmas and offer social workers a practical heuristic for identifying and resolving ethical conflicts in policy engagement.

The seven policy strategies identified in this study emerged from a cantonal policymaking process embedded within Switzerland's unique direct democratic institutional framework. Consequently, the extent to which these findings can be generalised to other political systems and cultural settings is limited. Nevertheless, the present results align closely with established theoretical frameworks (Gal & Weiss-Gal, 2023a; Jansson, 2018; Rieger, 2021) and prior research (e.g. Dauti & Bejko, 2024, 2025; Gal & Weiss-Gal, 2025). Based on this growing body of cross-national knowledge, the seven policy strategies' relevance can be theoretically transferred and empirically tested in similar contexts, both nationally and internationally. For instance, at the state level in the United States and in Switzerland, "the instruments of the referendum and the popular initiative are practically the same, and one can find many similarities in their use. For an assessment of direct democracy, it may thus be most useful to compare their experiences" (Linder & Mueller, 2021, p. 213). Additionally, future research could draw on contrasting cases, such as less direct democratic or more centralised political contexts, or cases in which social workers initiate rather than oppose policy, to deepen our understanding of social workers' policy engagement.

Beyond these contextual boundaries, several additional limitations warrant attention. First, while describing the policy strategies of actively engaged social workers, this study did not examine the factors that influence their levels and forms of engagement. Further studies may draw on more inclusive samples of practitioners, including inactive or less active participants, to further explain the varying degrees and forms of social workers' policy engagement. Additionally, the participants in this case study opposed a negative policy development rather than proactively advocating for positive change. Further research should also examine cases where social workers were the initiators rather than opponents of policy,

to analyse whether these different positions correspond to different policy strategies. Finally, although this study identified various policy strategies employed by social workers, it did not assess their impact. Future work should evaluate which strategies prove effective in specific temporal, political, and cultural contexts, thereby furthering our understanding of social workers' policy engagement.

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CHAPTER 5 – DISCUSSION

This dissertation examined the policy engagement of social workers in Switzerland through an in-depth analysis of their involvement in the policy process surrounding the proposed reductions in social assistance in the canton of Bern between 2012 and 2019. Although social workers are normatively expected to contribute to shaping social policy (e.g. AvenirSocial, 2026; BASW, 2021; IASSW & IFSW, 2014), empirical knowledge about their actual participation in policymaking remains limited (Gal & Weiss-Gal, 2023b; Kindler, 2021; Leiber et al., 2023; Weiss-Gal, 2016, 2017). Addressing this gap, the dissertation drew on the Bern case to explore when, how, and why social workers in specific roles adopt particular strategies at different stages of the policy process.

The dissertation followed an article-based format comprising three interrelated papers, presented as Chapters 2–4. Adopting a conceptual perspective, Chapter 2 addressed the first research question by analysing the key political institutions in Switzerland and examining how these institutions influence social workers' policy engagement. Chapter 3 responded to the second and third research questions by zooming in on the contested Bern case. Drawing on thematic analysis of interviews and documentary sources, it reconstructed the unfolding of this policy process and investigated when, how, and in which roles social workers became involved. Chapter 4 further developed the third research question by providing a deeper account of the strategies employed by social workers to influence the policy process in Bern. Based on thematic analysis of interviews with social workers engaged in the case, it identified and described seven distinct policy strategies in detail.

This concluding chapter synthesises the main findings from Chapters 2–4 and discusses how these results contribute to advancing the conceptual, empirical, and practical discourse on social workers' policy engagement. It also reflects on the study's limitations, offers directions for future research and closes with a brief concluding section.

5.1 Synthesis of the main findings

Drawing on the Swiss political system and the Bern case as its empirical foundation, this dissertation examined social workers' policy engagement through three interrelated research questions: (1) What are the key political institutions in Switzerland and how do they affect social workers' policy engagement? (2) When, and in which roles, do social workers become involved in policy processes? (3) What policy engagement strategies do social workers employ? The following sections synthesise the study's main findings in relation to these three dimensions, followed by a discussion of how the timing, roles and strategies of social workers' policy engagement in the studied case interacted.

5.1.1 Political institutions and policy engagement

Previous research has sought to explain why and how social workers engage in policymaking (e.g. Kim et al., 2023; Krips et al., 2024; Nouman et al., 2023; Ritter, 2008; Schwartz-Tayri, 2021). Drawing on this body of research, Gal and Weiss-Gal (2023) developed the Policy Engagement Conceptual Framework, which posits that social workers' policy engagement is shaped by individual motivation, organisational facilitation, opportunities within the political system, and the broader socio-economic and professional environments. Existing studies, however, have primarily concentrated on motivational and organisational factors, whereas considerably less attention has been given to how political opportunities and the broader social and professional environments influence social workers' participation in policy processes (Gal & Weiss-Gal, 2020). Addressing this gap, the present study examined Switzerland's key political institutions and how they affect social workers' policy engagement. Based on three illustrative case examples in Chapter 2 and an in-depth analysis of social workers' involvement in the Bern case, findings show how the institutions of federalism, the consensus system and semi-direct democracy provide opportunities for social workers to influence policy.

First, Switzerland's pronounced federal structure requires both horizontal and vertical coordination among actors operating at the national, cantonal, and local levels (Mueller & Vatter, 2020). This means that policy processes typically involve extensive negotiation across different layers of government as well as between actors situated at the same level.

Horizontally, organisations and individuals within the same tier of government frequently maintain close contact in order to exchange information, coordinate positions, and plan joint initiatives (Sager et al., 2017). In the canton of Bern, for instance, all 66 social services collaborated to establish the Bern Conference of Social Welfare and Child Protection (BKSE), a body designed to facilitate communication, coordination, and collective action among social services. Such horizontal cooperation, in turn, facilitates collective interest representation at the vertical level (Ladner, 2019; Linder & Mueller, 2021; Mueller & Vatter, 2020). In the examined case study, for example, BKSE leaders regularly represented the interests of local social services at the cantonal level, where legislation on social assistance is formulated. Furthermore, all levels of Switzerland's federal political system feature both executive and legislative bodies, which allows social workers to hold political office in government and parliament positions (Kindler, 2025). During the policy deliberations in the Bern case, four social workers made use of this route to influence policy from within the cantonal parliament.

Second, the Swiss political system can be characterised as a consensus democracy, contrasting with the model of majoritarian democracy (Lijphart, 2012). The three central features of this consensus system are governing coalitions composed of the strongest political parties, the cooperative behaviour of these parties in parliament, and the involvement of relevant actors before, during, and after the parliamentary phase of political decision-making (Linder & Mueller, 2021). For social workers, the third feature is particularly salient, as they are frequently invited to contribute their professional expertise in consensus-seeking

processes through formal consultations, roundtables, and parliamentary committees (Federal Council, 2022; Kehl, 2023). The examined case study in the canton of Bern vividly illustrates how the consensus system provides social workers with meaningful opportunities to influence policy through insider strategies. For example, leaders of AvenirSocial and BKSE, together with social services directors, submitted statements and offered expertise during the agenda-setting, policy formulation, and parliamentary decision phases, both in written and oral form. Moreover, social workers participated in parliamentary debates as members of parliament, with some actively seeking to build bridges with representatives of more conservative factions. Finally, the roundtable discussions initiated by the government when parliamentary deliberations stalled provided yet another arena for social workers to engage in consensus-oriented dialogue.

Third, complementing the consensus system and federalism, the Swiss political system is distinguished by the availability of direct democratic instruments at the local, cantonal, and national levels (Kehl, 2023). This means that citizens not only elect their representatives in parliament and government but also regularly participate in votes on specific policy matters. More precisely, the popular initiative enables interest groups to propose constitutional amendments, whereas the referendum functions as a mechanism to contest legislation adopted by parliament. Compared with purely representative democracies, these instruments offer two main opportunities for social workers to engage politically: they can participate in or lead signature-collection campaigns to initiate popular votes, and they can mobilise citizens to vote as well as exercise their own voting rights (Linder & Iff, 2011; Linder & Mueller, 2021; Moth et al., 2024). The case study in Bern clearly illustrates this potential. When social workers' attempts to influence parliamentary decisions through insider strategies proved unsuccessful, they turned to direct democratic means, such as joining the referendum committee, collecting signatures, mobilising voters, and raising public awareness. This case vividly demonstrates

how direct democracy can function as an additional avenue for policy engagement: whereas in a purely representative democracy the parliamentary approval of reductions to social assistance would have marked the final legislative decision, the referendum enabled these cuts to be contested and ultimately overturned.

5.1.2 Phases and roles in the policy process

In addition to examining the general opportunities that Switzerland's political institutions provide for policy engagement, this study used the specific case of Bern to investigate when, and in what roles, social workers participated in this particular policy process. To address this research question, the analysis presented in Chapter 3 identified the main phases of the Bern case, the roles assumed by social workers within it, and the intersections between these phases and roles.

As outlined in Table 1, the Bern policy case was reconstructed along four main phases: the agenda-setting phase, the policy formulation phase, the parliamentary decision phase, and the direct democratic decision phase. The process began in 2012, when, in the wake of mounting national criticism of social welfare from conservative factions, the Swiss People's Party placed a ten per cent reduction in social assistance on the cantonal political agenda. The subsequent policy formulation phase was highly contested, with the government's drafts facing strong criticism from both experts and party leaders. Only after a prolonged process of consensus-seeking negotiations did the government submit a final draft to parliament in 2017. During the parliamentary decision phase in 2017 and 2018, lawmakers made minor amendments to the bill and ultimately approved an eight per cent reduction. Parallel to the parliamentary process, actors from outside the legislature mobilised against the planned cuts. A broad alliance successfully gathered enough signatures in the direct democratic decision phase to trigger a referendum in 2019, in which the proposed reductions in social assistance were ultimately rejected by the electorate (Keller, 2025; Moth et al., 2024).

Table 1. *Overview of the Bern policy phases and social workers' involvement*

Roles	Agenda-Setting	Policy Formulation	Parliamentary Decision	Direct Democratic Decision
AvenirSocial leaders	X	X	X	X
BKSE leaders	X	X	X	X
Members of parliament	X	X	X	X
Social services directors	X	X	X	X
Critical social workers		X	X	
Social services social workers	*	X	X	X
Verkehrt activists		X	X	X

Note. *Social workers employed by the social services played only a minor role during the agenda-setting phase by writing letters to the editor.

Social workers were involved during all these phases of the policy process through a range of roles that can be grouped into more formal and more informal categories. AvenirSocial leaders, BKSE leaders, members of parliament and social services directors were categorised as formal roles, while critical social workers, social services social workers and Verkehrt activists were considered to be informal. This categorisation reveals an important overarching pattern, illustrated in Table 1: While all social workers in formal roles were consistently involved throughout the Bern case, the majority of those in informal roles only became engaged during the policy formulation phase, once the extent of the reduction in social assistance became apparent. This pattern could be explained by the fact that social workers in formal roles are, by nature of their professional and political positions, involved from the early stages of the policy process, whereas critical and activist social workers generally require time to become aware of an issue, organise, and build momentum before they can intervene in policy debates. This finding also aligns with previous research indicating that social workers in managerial roles are more involved in policy activities than frontline practitioners (Burzlaff et al., under review; Kim et al., 2023; Weiss-Gal & Gal, 2020). A further explanation may lie in the specific nature of the Bern case. The process was initiated through a parliamentary motion, which made it more accessible to formal policy actors during its early stages. In policy processes where change is

initiated by social workers outside of managerial or political positions, different patterns of engagement across formal and informal roles would be expected, i.e. frontline, critical or activist social workers may be the ones to place particular issues on the policy agenda through protest activities (see, e.g. Atteberry-Ash et al., 2023; Grodofsky & Makaros, 2016).

5.1.3 Strategies of policy engagement

The third research question centred on the policy strategies that social workers employed in the Bern case. This question was addressed through two separate analyses. The first, drawing on documentary evidence and interview transcripts, located policy strategies at the intersection of social workers' roles and the specific phases of the Bern case in which these strategies emerged (Chapter 3). This analysis identified the following policy strategies: influencing policymakers, organising protest activities, mobilising direct democracy, conducting media and public relations, and serving in parliament.

The second analysis, presented in Chapter 4, focused on the perspectives of the interviewed social workers. Based on the interview transcripts, it offers a more fine-grained account of how practitioners themselves conceptualised and enacted policy engagement. From this perspective, the following policy strategies emerged: influencing formal policymaking, shaping public opinion, building coalitions, mobilising engagement, creating emotional involvement, contributing professional knowledge, and involving service users.

To characterise these identified policy strategies in more abstract terms, the theoretical concepts introduced in Chapter 1 offer a useful heuristic across three dimensions. The first concerns the target of policy strategies. Burzlaff (2025) and Guidi et al. (2025) differentiate between internal strategies, aimed at influencing organisational policies, and external strategies, directed towards the formulation of public policy at local, regional, state or international level. In the Bern case, all identified strategies targeted policy formulation at the cantonal level and can therefore be characterised as entirely external.

The second dimension relates to the mode of influence, captured through the insider-outsider typology (Almog-Bar, 2018; Binderkrantz, 2005; Carbert, 2004; Grant, 2004). The analysis demonstrated that social workers employed both insider strategies, involving direct engagement with policymakers, and outsider strategies, which sought to influence the policy process indirectly by mobilising the public through both conflictual and non-conflictual means.

The final dimension concerns the strategy of involving service users and differentiates between different forms of such involvement. Rieger (2014, 2021) distinguishes between representing strategies, undertaken on behalf of service users, and activating strategies, aimed at mobilising service users' own policy engagement. Extending this conceptualisation, this dissertation provides evidence for a third form of service user involvement, namely collaborating strategies, in which social workers and service users act jointly. A prominent illustration is their shared participation in the Verkehrt group. Although the case study revealed instances of representing, collaborating and activating forms of service user involvement, representing strategies clearly predominated in social workers' practice.

Taken together, the policy strategies of social workers in the Bern case can be characterised across these three dimensions as predominantly representing service users through both insider and outsider approaches targeting external policymaking at the cantonal level.

5.1.4 Interaction of timing, roles and strategies of policy engagement

An additional key insight emerging at the intersection of the three research questions is that the timing and roles of social workers' engagement in the Bern case were closely linked to the policy strategies they employed. Examining these interrelations sheds light on how these strategies were selected, adapted, and combined in accordance with specific roles and across the various phases of the case.

The analysis identified a range of strategies that were conceptually grouped into insider and outsider approaches (Cailleux, 2025; De Corte & Roose, 2020), or, in the terminology

used by Guidi et al. (2025), into direct and indirect strategies. Of these, the outsider approach of using media and public relations was the most consistently employed, appearing throughout all phases and across almost all role types. This aligns with earlier work emphasising the significance of traditional and social media as tools for policy engagement (Dauti & Bejko, 2025; Manyama & Mvungi, 2017). In contrast to media and public relations, other strategies followed a more phase-specific pattern. In the agenda setting, policy formulation and early parliamentary decision phases of the Bern case, social workers relied strongly on insider strategies, including sending letters to policymakers, submitting consultation statements, and providing testimony before legislative committees. However, given the dominant conservative-right majority in both parliament and government, these efforts achieved limited results. As a consequence, social workers increasingly turned to outsider strategies, such as petitions, flash mobs, demonstrations and involvement in the referendum process. While insider and outsider approaches coexisted during the policy formulation and parliamentary decision phases, the period after parliamentary approval of the cuts saw engagement shift almost entirely to outsider strategies, culminating in the direct democratic referendum campaign. Overall, these findings demonstrate how the different stages of the policy case affected and interacted with social workers' strategic repertoire: initially attempting to influence policymakers directly, subsequently organising protest activities, and ultimately mobilising instruments of direct democracy. This trajectory highlights how shifting structural and temporal conditions – including political majorities, the availability of direct-democratic tools or time-bound opportunities such as the short signature-collection period – shaped the evolving strategic repertoire of social workers (Gal & Weiss-Gal, 2020, 2023).

In addition to the interaction between the different phases of the policy case and the strategies employed, the findings indicate that the roles of social workers were also closely

linked to their strategic choices. Those in more formalised positions in parliamentary or administrative settings, such as social work members of parliament, BKSE representatives, and directors of social services, tended to favour insider strategies, including lobbying and legislative work. In contrast, Verkehrt activists, critical social workers and frontline social workers were clearly more involved in indirect outsider strategies, notably protest activities and referendum campaigning. AvenirSocial leaders occupied a distinctive position, consistently employing a blend of insider and outsider methods: they engaged in lobbying efforts while also contributing to the organisation of protest initiatives. These observations align with contemporary debates in political science that question the rigidity of the insider-outsider concept. From this perspective, AvenirSocial and its leadership may be viewed as “unnatural insiders” (O’Brien et al., 2023), as they are typically outside actors yet have the resources, expertise, and networks to implement both insider and outsider strategies (Almog-Bar, 2018; Cailleux, 2025). Yet, AvenirSocial leaders were not alone in combining approaches. Practitioners in almost all roles used media and public relations alongside other strategies. For example, social workers in parliament supplemented their institutional work with press statements or participation in public discussions, while BKSE leaders paired lobbying engagement with informational events for the general public. Similarly, Verkehrt activists deliberately staged protest activities as a means of drawing media coverage. Overall, these findings suggest that social workers’ involvement in policymaking emerges from a dynamic interaction between their roles and their strategic choices, with diverse strategies often used concurrently to strengthen one another.

5.2 Implications

The findings of this dissertation entail several implications for advancing theoretical perspectives on social workers’ policy engagement, as well as for informing practice in politically contested environments. The following sections address these two dimensions in

turn, beginning with the study's contributions to theory and proceeding to its practical implications for social work.

5.2.1 Theoretical implications

Using the Swiss political system, and the Bern case in particular, this study advances understanding of how political institutions shape social workers' policy engagement. The findings show that the availability of direct democratic instruments opened an additional and heavily used avenue for influence. This provides empirical support for the Policy Engagement Conceptual Framework's claim that social workers' policy involvement is shaped by the concrete opportunities available to them to affect policy processes (Gal & Weiss-Gal, 2015 2023). Although this study presents initial insights into a field that has received limited empirical attention, further work is needed to clarify how political institutions interact with social workers' policy engagement across diverse political systems, cultural contexts and professional settings (Gal & Weiss-Gal, 2020).

The study also contributes nuance to emerging discussions on political timing (e.g. De Corte & Roose, 2020; Klammer et al., 2019; McGregor & Millar, 2020) by demonstrating that social workers' strategies evolve as a policy process unfolds. Reconstructing engagement across four distinct phases highlights that their approaches are dynamic rather than static. This insight extends previous research that has largely examined policy involvement from a cross-sectional perspective or has addressed only a single phase. Moreover, while existing scholarship typically situates social workers' policy engagement within agenda-setting, formulation, implementation and evaluation (Benz & Rieger, 2015; De Corte & Roose, 2020; Klammer et al., 2019), this study shows the analytical necessity of also including the decision-making phase. Bringing this phase into conceptual and empirical analyses enables a fuller understanding of how social workers lobby within formal legislative arenas as well as in wider democratic processes during the pivotal moment of decision-making (Rieger, 2024).

Furthermore, the study advances an understanding of policy strategies structured across three dimensions. Building on existing approaches that focus on the targets of policy engagement (Burzlaff 2025; Guidi et al., 2025), insider-outsider modes of influence (Binderkrantz, 2005; Cailleux, 2025; Grant, 2000, 2004) and the forms of service user involvement (Rieger, 2014, 2021), this dissertation argues that integrating these three dimensions within a single framework enables a nuanced characterisation of social workers' policy strategies. In the first dimension, strategies can be distinguished according to whether they target internal organisational measures or external policies at the local, regional, national or international level. The second dimension captures variation in the involvement of service users: representing strategies are undertaken on their behalf, collaborating strategies are conducted jointly with them, and activating strategies mobilise their own policy engagement. The third dimension differentiates between insider approaches, which seek to influence policy through direct engagement with policymakers, and outsider approaches, which aim to mobilise the public. Taken together, the integration of these three dimensions offers a comprehensive analytical lens for characterising social workers' policy strategies in terms of their targets of engagement, their modes of influence and their forms of service user involvement.

The study also identifies the creation of emotional involvement as a distinct and previously underexplored policy strategy. While emotions have increasingly been recognised as integral to social work practice (e.g. Ingram, 2015; O'Connor, 2022; Sicora, 2022, 2026), earlier research has not conceptualised emotional dynamics as components of policy engagement. This study demonstrates that creating emotional involvement can serve as a deliberate means of raising public awareness, influencing policymakers or mobilising engagement. Emotional involvement therefore constitutes a cross-cutting form of policy engagement that may be deployed within both insider and outsider strategies and that can be relevant across multiple phases of a policy process. By foregrounding the significance of

emotions in policy engagement, this study invites further scholarship to examine more closely when, how and why social workers draw on emotional dynamics in their political work.

Finally, by examining how strategies, timing and professional roles interact, this study challenges the tendency to analyse these dimensions separately. One of its central contributions is to demonstrate how strategies were selected, adapted and combined across roles and phases. This supports a shift towards more dynamic conceptualisations of policy engagement that situate social workers' actions in relation to their professional roles and the changing political environment. The findings have implications for both theoretical and empirical work. Theoretically, models such as the Policy Engagement Conceptual Framework (Gal & Weiss-Gal, 2023) could incorporate temporal and role-specific variations as an additional layer for understanding when and how social workers engage in policy. For example, the route of holding elected office – linked to the role of a social work politician – becomes most salient during policy formulation and parliamentary decision-making, while its relevance diminishes in other phases. Likewise, Figueira-McDonough's (1993) methods of policy practice are contingent on temporal conditions; reform through litigation, for instance, can only be pursued after a policy has been adopted. Empirically, much existing research relies on cross-sectional quantitative approaches (Weiss-Gal, 2017; for examples, see Burzlaff et al., 2025; Carvalho et al., 2025; Guidi et al., 2025). Future research would benefit from approaches that allow the concurrent examination of roles, strategies and timing, such as longitudinal studies, case analyses or ethnographic fieldwork. Such designs would enable scholars to further explore how these dimensions of social workers' policy engagement interact.

5.2.2 Practical implications

In addition to its theoretical contributions, this study offers several practical implications for strengthening social workers' engagement in policy processes. A central lesson emerging from the Bern case is the importance of earlier and more anticipatory forms of policy

engagement. Social workers, especially those in informal roles, often entered the process only after formal decisions had already narrowed institutional pathways, meaning their interventions largely amounted to contesting already-established facts. Early agenda-setting occurred within administrative and political arenas in which social workers were scarcely represented, limiting their capacity to shape the reform's trajectory. Developing anticipatory capacities would help counter this pattern. Such capacities include systematic monitoring of political developments, policy alerts, involvement in pre-parliamentary debates, and sustained relationship-building with policymakers through regular exchanges. More explicit scenario-based thinking, for example anticipating how committee decisions or shifts in political majorities may affect emerging proposals, would further support well-timed strategic engagement. Such anticipatory approaches would make it possible to contribute professional expertise before proposals become entrenched and public narratives are defined by others. As such monitoring and analytical activities may be too resource-intensive for individual practitioners, professional associations, their leaders or designated staff with specialised policy expertise could assume these functions, allowing social workers to shift from reactive involvement to more proactively positioned policy engagement.

A second implication relates to the relevance of purposeful and sustained coalition-building. The Bern case illustrates that the effectiveness of policy engagement hinges not only on individual action but also on the collective capacity of the profession to act in a coordinated manner. Social workers participated through multiple roles and represented a variety of organisations and groups, which meant that their efforts were not always strategically aligned. In an attempt to bring these approaches together, Verkehrt activists organised "Bazar" meetings, though these attracted mainly informal actors. This experience indicates that future engagement could be strengthened by establishing broader and more inclusive platforms that clarify roles, communication channels, and strategic priorities at an

early stage of a policy process. Such platforms could enable continuous inter-group deliberation; identify converging and diverging policy positions and strategies; minimise duplication or contradictory action; and coordinate the use of varied approaches, including the concurrent deployment of insider and outsider strategies. Establishing such platforms on a permanent rather than ad-hoc basis would reduce the organisational effort required to join forces and enable coalitions to respond more swiftly when policy windows open.

The Bern case further illustrates that technical expertise alone rarely suffices to shape political and public debate, particularly in highly polarised environments. Opponents of social assistance anchored their claims in emotionally charged narratives that centred on presumed laziness and misuse, thereby activating powerful stereotypes. In contrast, social workers' early interventions relied predominantly on technical reasoning, which proved only partially effective. This dynamic reflects Lakoff's (2014) argument that ideological frames exert stronger influence on political attitudes than empirical evidence. According to Lakoff, when confronted with information that challenges their established frame, individuals often dismiss the inconvenient evidence rather than adjust their underlying assumptions. Building on these insights, the dissertation argues for combining empirical evidence with emotionally resonant framing to strengthen the effectiveness of policy engagement. This may involve using storytelling, challenging stigmatising narratives and communicating through traditional and social media with clear, accessible messaging when contributing professional expertise to public and political discourses.

The findings also underscore that involving service users can function as a cross-cutting strategy across several forms of policy engagement. In the Bern case, social workers encouraged service users to join protests, employ direct democratic instruments and participate in grassroots organisations opposing the cuts. Nonetheless, service user involvement largely took the form of representing and collaborating strategies, whereas

activating strategies aimed at fostering autonomous engagement were less visible. To widen and deepen participation, social workers could develop permanent structures that support continuous dialogue with service users on emerging policy issues. This could include advisory forums, co-produced advocacy initiatives or training opportunities for those interested in civic engagement. Such measures could help promote a more inclusive approach to policy engagement, including more empowering forms of involvement. At the same time, active involvement of service users requires careful ethical reflection. While their cooperation within the system of social assistance – much like in other areas of social work – is compulsory, their engagement in policy processes must remain voluntary and safeguarded against instrumentalisation (Weiss-Gal et al., 2024).

Finally, the study invites reflection on educational implications. The Bern case demonstrates that effective policy engagement requires familiarity with political institutions, an understanding of relevant policymaking venues, and practical skills for influencing policy processes. Yet many of these competencies are insufficiently developed within existing training pathways. This gap is particularly evident in the German-speaking context, where social work curricula contain comparatively little policy-oriented content (Burzlaff, 2022; Kachel, 2022; Schmidbauer & Kachel, 2023). Strengthening education and continuing professional development in this domain is therefore essential. Previous scholarship has argued that policy education is most effective when it not only provides theoretical grounding in political institutions and policy processes but also actively promotes applied skills (Burzlaff et al., under review; Schwartz-Tayri, 2021; Schwartz-Tayri et al. 2021). Illustrative approaches include involving students in real-world policy projects, writing letters to editors, producing podcasts, attending parliamentary debates, or engaging directly with elected officials (e.g. Chiang & Lin, 2025; Elmaliach-Mankita et al. 2019; Henman, 2012; Kilbane et al., 2013; Lohmeyer, 2025; Martin et al., 2022; Redmond et al., 2023; Rieger & Wurtzbacher,

2020; Wang et al., 2022; Weiss-Gal & Peled, 2009; Weiss-Gal & Savaya, 2012). Such pedagogical strategies can equip future practitioners with the concrete skillsets required for meaningful and effective policy engagement.

5.3 Limitations and future directions

The findings of this dissertation are subject to several limitations that restrict their broader applicability and point to areas for further research. First, the analysis is shaped by its focus on a single case embedded within Switzerland's direct democratic, consensus-oriented and federalist political system, which raises questions about the transferability of the findings. The study is among the first to empirically examine how political institutions influence social workers' engagement in policy processes. However, it is anchored in a case situated within an institutional configuration that offers specific opportunities for policy engagement, particularly through instruments of direct democracy, which may not exist in the same form elsewhere. As such, the generalisability of the findings beyond the Bern context is limited. Comparative studies, both in systems with similar institutional arrangements and in more centralised or less participatory political settings, are needed to further delineate how political structures shape the extent and forms of social workers' policy engagement.

The nature of the policy process under examination constitutes a second limitation. Social workers' engagement in the Bern case centred on opposition to a detrimental reform rather than the initiation of new policy proposals. Consequently, the policy strategies identified here reflect an oppositional mode of engagement. It remains unclear whether social workers adopt different strategic repertoires or temporal patterns when they act as policy initiators. Future research should therefore investigate cases in which social workers proactively advance policy ideas to assess whether distinct forms of engagement emerge.

A third limitation concerns the unit of analysis. The dissertation centred on individual practitioners' engagement, resulting in only limited attention to collective actors such as

professional organisations, social services and trade unions. Although these groups appeared in the case study through the actions and perspectives of their individual representatives, their internal dynamics, strategic orientations and policy-related decision-making were not examined. Given that individual policy engagement is frequently constrained by limited resources, time and skills, future research should examine how collective social work actors participate in policy processes and how their forms of engagement diverge from those of individual practitioners (see, e.g. Einhorn et al., 2026; Schein, 2026).

A fourth limitation relates to the sampling strategy. Focusing exclusively on practitioners who were actively involved in the Bern reform process enabled the generation of rich empirical insights into forms of active policy engagement. However, this approach excluded the perspectives of social workers who were only marginally involved or who chose not to engage at all. Their accounts may reveal forms of engagement that are less visible in public arenas, as well as structural, organisational or personal barriers that inhibit policy involvement. Broadening the participant base in future research would thus enable a more comprehensive understanding of how and why engagement varies across the profession.

Finally, although the study identified a wide range of policy strategies employed by social workers, it did not assess their effectiveness. As in the wider literature, the question of strategic impact – why particular approaches succeed or fail within specific political, institutional and cultural contexts – remains underexplored. Addressing this gap would require methodological approaches capable of tracing policy outcomes, examining causal mechanisms and capturing longer-term effects of engagement. Advancing such analyses would contribute to theoretical accounts of policy influence and provide practice-oriented guidance on how social workers can more effectively shape the policies that affect service users' daily lives and the profession's institutional environment.

5.4. Conclusion

This dissertation set out to advance knowledge on social workers' policy engagement by examining their involvement in the contested reform of social assistance in the canton of Bern between 2012 and 2019. By situating the analysis within the Swiss political system and the concrete Bern case, the study sought to develop a contextualised understanding of when, how and in what roles social workers participate in policymaking. In doing so, it offers one of the few detailed reconstructions of a real-world policy process in which social workers intervened, thereby contributing to the expanding scholarship on policy engagement in four key respects.

First, the dissertation addressed a significant gap in the literature concerning the influence of political institutions on social workers' policy engagement. Existing research has predominantly centred on individual motivations and organisational facilitation, with comparatively limited attention to institutional opportunity structures. By analysing Switzerland's federalist, consensus-oriented and direct democratic system, and by tracing how these institutions operated in the Bern case, the study demonstrated how political institutions shape both the extent and the forms of social workers' engagement. The availability of direct democratic instruments emerged as a particularly important avenue for influence. As one of the first empirical investigations to examine the relationship between political institutions and policy engagement, the dissertation offers a conceptual and empirical basis for future studies.

Second, the findings demonstrate that social workers' strategies are not static but evolve as policy processes unfold. This advances earlier scholarship, which has predominantly examined policy involvement through cross-sectional designs or by focusing on a single phase, and has therefore been unable to capture how social workers adjust and recalibrate their strategies across different stages of a policy reform. In this respect, the dissertation also underscores the decision-making phase as a pivotal moment within a policy case – one in which social workers can, should, and indeed do engage.

Third, the dissertation advances a conceptualisation of policy strategies structured along three dimensions: the focus of action (internal organisational or external policies at local, regional, national and international level), the mode of influence (insider or outsider strategies) and the orientation towards service users (representing, collaborating or activating). This framework integrates existing typologies of policy strategies and offers a structured basis for comparative work and further conceptual development.

Fourth, by examining how strategies, timing and professional roles interact, this study challenges the tendency to analyse these dimensions in isolation. The findings show that strategies were selected, adapted and combined across roles and phases, indicating a need for more dynamic conceptualisations of policy engagement. Theoretically, this suggests that existing frameworks should account for temporal and role-specific variations as an additional layer for understanding when, how and why social workers engage in policy. Empirically, these insights point to the value of research designs that enable the concurrent examination of roles, strategies and timing in order to further illuminate how these dimensions of social workers' policy engagement interact.

In conclusion, the dissertation provides one of the few empirical insights into social workers' engagement within a real policy process. Drawing on the Bern case, it develops a nuanced account of when and how social workers participate in policymaking, the roles they assume and the political institutions that provide opportunities for their engagement. Across these dimensions, the study advances theoretical concepts and formulates practical implications with the goal to further strengthen policy engagement as one of the core aspects of the social work profession.

5.5 References

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